

1 **Learning Environments with Other Animals**

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9

10 **Abstract**

11 *The question of how humans have come to know their environments and how such knowledge*
12 *is accrued and deployed has gained novel significance in an age of deepening ecological crisis.*
13 *Engaging with this long-standing issue, this article draws attention to overlooked more-than-*
14 *human contexts of environmental knowledge-making. We suggest that studying processes of*
15 *human environmental learning from a multispecies perspective can transform our*
16 *understanding of past human-environment relationships. We begin with an outline of the deeply*
17 *entrenched anthropocentrism that has shaped concepts of knowledge and learning in the*
18 *European(-derived) tradition. We then propose a framework to facilitate interdisciplinary*
19 *investigations into the interspecies dimension of human environmental learning in the form of*
20 *a tripartite heuristic of learning through, learning from and learning with other animals. With*
21 *particular emphasis on the third and most complex modality, we discuss how this scheme can*
22 *provide new insights into how humans and other animals have inspired each other to act and*
23 *dwell in past shared landscapes, with lasting consequences for broader historical trajectories*

24 *including material culture, cognition, and discourse. Since such interspecies dynamics have*
25 *rarely been addressed in historical scholarship, the article draws together a range of examples*
26 *and contexts in which learning with other animals appears to have been a history-shaping*
27 *dynamic, comprising such variegated societies as Pleistocene and early Holocene North*
28 *European hunter-gatherers, Indigenous Arctic foragers, and North American Plains horse*
29 *pastoralists. Based on these explorations of human environmental learning, we suggest that*
30 *interspecies learning mechanisms can provide a multispecies analog of lateral gene transfer*
31 *for more-than-human history and multispecies archaeology, help us integrate human history*
32 *into animal history and the broader history of the biosphere, and hold implications for future-*
33 *making conversations on reimagining our coexistence with other earthlings.*

34

35 **Keywords:** More-than-human history; multispecies archaeology; human-animal relations;
36 environment; knowledge; learning

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54

55 **Introduction**

56 The question of how humans come to know and understand environments has been a long-
57 standing research problem across the cultural and ecological sciences, gaining new significance
58 in the context of deepening global environmental crises.¹ Environmental knowledge has been
59 understood as a key source of human action and, potentially, a key reason for transformative
60 change in how people interact with their nonhuman surroundings.² It is increasingly understood
61 as pluralized and heterogeneous, given that different human cultures and lifeways can promote
62 different modes of attending to and knowing environments. In this vein, Western scientific
63 knowledge of “the environment” has been contrasted with a wide range of localized
64 environmental knowledges, moving “Traditional Ecological Knowledge” (TEK) to the center
65 of broader debates about nature conservation and ecological stewardship.

66 In this article, we suggest that these conversations can greatly benefit from careful
67 interdisciplinary examination of the ways in which people in the past and deep past have
68 familiarized themselves with, and adapted to, novel environmental conditions. Such a
69 perspective must consider the possibilities and intricacies of *learning* environments, the
70 cultural biases involved in such learning processes, and how the latter relate to regimes of
71 ecological knowledge and sense-making. In tackling this issue, we propose that environmental
72 learning has often occurred as a distributed process in what anthropologist Tim Ingold has
73 called “sentient ecologies”³ and involved not just human beings but also broader multispecies
74 assemblages. Here, we are especially interested in the role of nonhuman animals not just as
75 environmental agents in a general sense but as teachers and guides — inspirations and models
76 for the human groups with whom they cohabit. In this way, we seek to complement

¹ See, for example, Moran, *People and Nature*.

² Coldicutt, “Environmental Knowing and Action.”

³ Ingold, *The Perception of the Environment*.

77 perspectives on environmental learning that have been framed in human-centered terms, as is
78 the case with Marcy Rockman’s notion of “landscape learning” developed for archaeological
79 investigations of how Pleistocene foragers made themselves at home in unfamiliar
80 environments.⁴ The term “learning environments” evokes both process and place —
81 environmental learning as a set of practices and the historically situated environments in which
82 such learning occurs in particular ways — in an attempt to address the distinctive sets of
83 opportunities and constraints different landscapes offer to, or impose upon, different types of
84 organisms and lifeways.

85 Animal-oriented investigations are increasingly regarded as a mainstay of history and
86 archaeology, dismantling deep-seated ideas about animal-human distinctions and critiquing
87 reductive understandings of animal contributions to human life and society in which animals
88 figure primarily as resources, symbols, or passive objects of human knowledge practices.⁵
89 However, so far little attention has been paid to how these developments might be brought to
90 bear on entrenched anthropocentric circumscriptions of both learning and knowledge. Human
91 learning is generally understood to be unparalleled in scope, potency, and evolutionary
92 implications, enabling the development of “cumulative culture” based on sophisticated
93 learning ecologies.⁶ In the humanities, discussions of the dimensions and dynamics of learning
94 have thus largely been limited to a focus on human-to-human processes at work in more or less
95 formalized systems of intrahuman socialization and education. But, as we wish to argue in this
96 article, an all-too-exclusive focus on human beings as uniquely “knowing animals”⁷ has not

⁴ Rockman, “Knowledge and Learning in the Archaeology of Colonization”; Rockman, “Landscape Learning in Relation to Evolutionary Theory.”

⁵ A few examples are Nance, *The Historical Animal*; Baratay, “Building an Animal History”; Specht, “Animal History after Its Triumph”; Ohrem, “A Declaration of Interdependence”; Roscher et al., *Handbook of Historical Animal Studies*. For works in archaeology, see Hill, “Archaeology and Animal Persons”; Hamilakis and Overton, “A Multi-Species Archaeology”; Sykes, *Beastly Questions*; Oma Armstrong, *The Sheep People*.

⁶ Haidle et al., *The Nature of Culture*; Migliano and Vinicius, “The Origins of Human Cumulative Culture.”

⁷ Tallis, *The Knowing Animal*.

97 only led us to underestimate the learning capacities of other species but also obscured how
98 human knowledge projects have themselves been shaped by historically situated
99 more-than-human entanglements. Taking seriously the active role of animals in histories of
100 human environmental learning means acknowledging that animals are adept learners in their
101 own right: that they embody potent ways of ecological knowing which have repeatedly made
102 animal behaviors and lifeways a privileged domain of human learning. The idea that animals
103 are learners implies that they are also *knowers* — holders of effective, reliable, and valuable
104 knowledge, rather than creatures whose perceptions of, and engagements with, their worlds are
105 delimited by biologically pre-set instincts that remain largely unaffected by experience.

106 Knowledge is a concept that is as contested as it is central to how we understand
107 ourselves and our role as humans in Earth’s history. In European philosophical traditions, it has
108 commonly been reserved for the highest echelons of organic life, regarded as a marker of
109 humans’ special place in the world they inhabit. In this anthropocentric perspective, humans
110 are able to move beyond their animality through their ability to reflexively relate to it,
111 privileging intellectual operations that seemingly transcend the immediacy and concreteness of
112 the lifeworld. Unlike, say, dogs or horses, whose relationship with their environment has been
113 typically construed as “largely fixed,” the worlds of humans require active construction,
114 underlining both the unique agentiality and constitutional vulnerability of creatures whose
115 “world-openness” enables and compels them to create uniquely *cultural* worlds.⁸

116 The classic — if now embattled — “justified true belief” (JTB) account of knowledge
117 holds that, in order to count as a knower, a subject must not only believe a true proposition but
118 also be (rationally) justified in doing so.⁹ Influential figures like Wilfrid Sellars and, in a

⁸ Berger and Luckmann, *The Social Construction of Reality*, 65. In this sense (according to Arnold Gehlen), the human being is a “special biological problem.” See Gehlen, *Man: His Nature and Place in the World*. Also see Ohrem, “An Address from Elsewhere.”

⁹ Turri, “Is Knowledge Justified True Belief?”; Dutant, “The Legend of the Justified True Belief Analysis.”

119 different way, Ernest Sosa have proposed further metacognitive criteria that effectively
120 distinguish human knowledge-making from epistemic processes at work among nonhuman
121 animals. According to Sosa, for example, it is the “special status” of higher order “reflective
122 knowledge” that distinguishes human cognition from “knowledge of the sort attainable by
123 beasts”.¹⁰ Varying in emphasis and orientation, such accounts have contributed to a cluster of
124 “differentialist” perspectives united in their insistence on strong qualitative differences between
125 human and animal ways of knowing — a picture we seek to complicate in this article.¹¹

126 We especially wish to contribute to the ongoing cross-disciplinary reappraisal of
127 human-animal relations by exploring, in a preliminary way, histories of animal-mediated forms
128 of human environmental learning, which we consider to be an underappreciated perspective on
129 the ways in which animal agentive ingenuity and worldmaking capacities have shaped human
130 histories. Interspecies learning has only recently been identified as a source of human and
131 nonhuman knowledge formation, even as traditional ethnographies are at times replete with
132 evidence of animal observation and mimicry as key cultural inputs. Following a brief
133 discussion of the concept of environmental learning, we present a tripartite heuristic of animal-
134 mediated environmental learning. We first consider what we call learning *through* animals, a
135 modality in which animals have often figured as disembodied, generalized, and largely
136 interchangeable abstractions. We distinguish this modality from, respectively, learning *from*
137 and learning *with* animals as two principal forms of learning shaped by historically situated,
138 embodied, and embedded animal others. Here, we focus most of our attention on historical
139 examples of learning *with* other animals, which we argue has often occurred in relatively

¹⁰ Sosa, “Human Knowledge, Animal and Reflective,” 291; Sosa, “Knowledge and Intellectual Virtue,” 242.

¹¹ For a discussion and critique of “differentialism,” see Glock, “Animals, Thoughts and Concepts”; Glock, “Non-Human Knowledge and Non-Human Agency.” Attempts at establishing clear distinctions between “lower” and “higher” forms of knowing and the relegation of the former to the animal side of the equation tie in with a longstanding philosophical project committed to identifying the parameters of human uniqueness and “determin[ing] human specificity over and against those beings who/that threaten to undermine that specificity.” Calarco, *Zoographies*, 52; Sorabji, *Animal Minds and Human Morals*.

140 durable and mutualistic (if rarely symmetrical) interspecies arrangements in particular shared
141 environments.

142

143 **Toward a More-than-Human Account of Human Environmental Learning**

144 As an important mechanism of knowledge generation and transmission, learning has figured
145 prominently in debates about the cultural evolution of human societies.¹² For our purposes,
146 learning can be understood as a dynamic process that bridges knowing and doing —
147 encompassing skills, behaviors, attitudes, and values — and that depends on different
148 “operators” such as observation, familiarization, imitation, systematization, analogization, and
149 experimentation. It is thus shaped by diverse factors and can involve various systematic biases
150 that influence how knowledge is acquired and applied. Emphasizing the embodied nature of
151 knowledge production in specific socioenvironmental contexts, we understand knowledge as
152 emerging from conditions of worldmaking that testify to what Michael Polanyi has called the
153 “kinship of knowing and living”.¹³ In its contents and consequences and in the methods of its
154 formation, knowledge is always “enworlded” and enacted by variously configured collectives
155 in a way that unsettles any strict separation between knowing and doing.¹⁴

156 In his classic *Personal Knowledge*, Polanyi directly addresses animal learning by
157 arguing that instances in which “an animal shares in the intelligent effort which another animal
158 is making in its presence” should be considered examples of a “true transmission of
159 knowledge” — not “blind parrot-like imitation,” but “real communication of knowledge on the
160 inarticulate level”.¹⁵ For Polanyi, the acquisition of “tacit knowledge” is rooted in “pure

¹² See e.g. Shennan, *Genes, Memes and Human History*; Mesoudi, *Cultural Evolution*; Ellis et al., “Evolving the Human Niche.”

¹³ Polanyi, *Personal Knowledge*, 404.

¹⁴ Descola, “Cognition, Perception and Worlding.”

¹⁵ Polanyi, *Personal Knowledge*, 206.

161 conviviality,” that is, in the desire for, and praxis of, cultivating “good fellowship” that humans
162 share with other social animals.¹⁶ He suggests that animals, too, inhabit a “heuristic field,”
163 which provides them with opportunities and with the task of making use of them, underlining
164 that “*knowing belongs to the class of achievements that are comprised by all forms of living*”.¹⁷
165 More recent works in naturalistic epistemology, such as those of Hilary Kornblith, have
166 rejected an overly restrictive emphasis on metacognitive reflective capacities, underlining
167 instead that the cognitive processes involved in knowledge production have evolved to help all
168 kinds of organisms interact effectively with their environments.¹⁸

169 As “interested” entities whose behaviors are guided by an elective openness to a world
170 “strewn with opportunities and risks,” animals provide crucial orientations and exemplars for
171 other beings, humans included.¹⁹ Roberto Marchesini argues that human life has been
172 “surrounded by animal knowledges,” and animals have long functioned as nonhuman
173 “knowledge *partners*” as well as “sources of fervid creativity for our species,” their influence
174 reaching deeply into what is usually conceived as an exclusively human cultural sphere.²⁰ It is
175 perhaps especially in the production and mobilization of *environmental* knowledge —
176 understood here as a body of actionable knowledge (know-that and know-how) that both
177 pertains to and emerges from specific human-environment configurations — that human
178 learning tends to exceed any strictly “human” domain. At its core, environmental knowledge
179 is a form of culturally mediated experiential-observational knowledge that develops and
180 transforms as different groups of humans respond to, negotiate, and modify the patterns of

¹⁶ Polanyi, *Personal Knowledge*, 210.

¹⁷ Polanyi, *Personal Knowledge*, 403, original emphasis.

¹⁸ Kornblith, *Knowledge and Its Place in Nature*; Kornblith, “Epistemology and Cognitive Ethology.”

¹⁹ Marchesini, *The Creative Animal*, 84.

²⁰ Marchesini, “The Theriosphere,” 114, 115. Marchesini captures this dependence on nonhuman animality in the evolution of human thought and the constitution of “plurispecific communities” – reductively understood as “human” societies – with his concept of “zoomimesis.” Marchesini, “The Theriosphere,” 115; also see Bird-David, *Us, Relatives*, chap. 5.

181 possibility for action — “affordances” in the language of ecological psychology²¹ — that
182 structure their modes of existence in specific environments. While actionability is a key
183 purpose of human learning more generally, it holds particular importance in the encounter with
184 unfamiliar environments (for example, in contexts of migration or displacement) or the
185 adaptation to environments that have become unfamiliar through significant environmental
186 change. However, like other types of cultural learning, environmental learning has an
187 inherently creative dimension and is not reducible to a set of responses to “deficiencies” or
188 “challenges.” It is shaped by the dynamic interplay between existing cultural frameworks and
189 environmental characteristics and thus defined by receptivity to forms of nonhuman agency.

190 Indigenous knowledges have provided important reference points and inspirations for
191 rethinking environmental learning in more-than-human terms. Ethnobotanist Robin Kimmerer
192 draws attention to the “grammar of animacy” at the heart of Indigenous ecologies and suggests
193 that (re)learning of this grammar — an act of listening to the myriad of nonhuman voices that
194 surround us and re-attuning human attention to this plentiful natural world — is among the
195 most pressing challenges.²² The important lesson is that environmental knowledge is often
196 rooted in learning with and from nonhumans, constituting *knowledge-making communities* of
197 a distinctly more-than-human nature. Knowledge of this sort is formed within ecologies
198 saturated with heterogeneous beings who, through their behavior, volition, memory, and
199 speech, invoke the possibility of sentience and invite engagement with their presence, agency,
200 and successful operation in their environments. Such environmental learning does not have to
201 be symmetrical, and indeed often won’t be. What is important is that it cannot be reduced to an
202 exclusively human affair in terms of agentiality, directionality, and the “sources” and parties
203 involved. It is also crucial to recognize that it varies in historical form and relevance, for

²¹ See Gibson, *The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception*; Chemero, “An Outline of a Theory of Affordances”; Jenkins, “Gibson’s ‘Affordances’: Evolution of a Pivotal Concept.”

²² Kimmerer, *Braiding Sweetgrass*.

204 example because sentience can be differentially ascribed or because different knowledge
205 partners can be drawn upon to learn and navigate particular environments based on particular
206 cultural frameworks. In short, we need to pay attention to how humans and nonhumans are
207 caught up in specific historical contexts that shape what they have to say to each other under
208 changing conditions.

209 A growing body of evidence from the sciences of animal behavior supports this
210 attention to environmental learning and to knowledge embodied in, and enacted by, animal
211 others. These fields have begun to challenge the idea of animal behavior as fixed by pre-given
212 action patterns tied to particular ecological milieus, an image traditionally juxtaposed with what
213 has been understood as the human prerogative of environmental and behavioral
214 underdeterminedness — that is, the relative freedom from pre-specified stimulus-response
215 patterns and a corresponding openness to multiple possible ways of acting in, and relating to,
216 a given environment. Evidence for animal “world-openness” comes, for example, in the form
217 of diverse animal cultures now documented across various genera,²³ and the long-
218 underestimated role of social learning (with evidence for nonhuman cumulative culture) even
219 in behavioral domains such as subsistence and mobility, which have often been treated as
220 governed by hard-wired behavioral patterns.²⁴ Evolutionary biologists now increasingly speak
221 of animal agency and niche construction, and report both phenotypic and behavioral plasticity
222 in many nonhuman organisms.²⁵ Scholars have also begun to recognize that contemporary
223 observations of animal behavior may register historically specific learning environments
224 (shaped by Anthropocene conditions) rather than unchanging and broadly generalizable species

²³ Ramsey, “Culture in Humans and Other Animals”; Whiten, “The Burgeoning Reach of Animal Culture”; Whitehead and Rendell, *The Cultural Lives of Whales and Dolphins*.

²⁴ Jesmer et al., “Is Ungulate Migration Culturally Transmitted?”; Slagsvold and Wiebe, “Social Learning in Birds and Its Role in Shaping a Foraging Niche”; Sasaki and Biro, “Cumulative Culture Can Emerge from Collective Intelligence in Animal Groups.”

²⁵ Odling-Smee et al., *Niche Construction*; West-Eberhard, *Developmental Plasticity and Evolution*; Walsh, *Organisms, Agency, and Evolution*; Natoli et al., “Coexistence between Humans and ‘Misunderstood’ Domestic Cats in the Anthropocene”; Read and Szokolszky, “What Animals Can Do.”

225 repertoires. For instance, human-accelerated warming of the Arctic and the associated
226 reshuffling of marine ecosystems have prompted orcas to develop new forms of behavior and
227 create novel ecological niches. At least three orca “ecotypes” are now widely recognized,
228 exemplifying different trajectories by which nonhuman animals can learn to adapt to
229 unprecedented environmental situations in real time.²⁶

230 As Jedediah Allen and Kristin Andrews have argued, our ability to appreciate how other
231 animals navigate their worlds is still hampered by an overriding conceptual bias that undercuts
232 our ability to recognize observational evidence for behavioral designations otherwise assumed
233 to be exclusive to humans.²⁷ The idea that learning is a sociological rather than an ecological
234 phenomenon further adds to this architecture of biases and blind spots, which is not only
235 anthropocentric but also tends to package learning processes tightly within the boundaries of
236 species. Cross- or interspecies learning is at present rarely considered in mainstream accounts
237 of learning, despite recent emphasis on the ways in which different organisms jointly shape
238 each other’s semiotic environments. Meerkat warning calls, for example, help other animals
239 navigate predatory landscapes. Similarly, vultures and other scavenging birds alert terrestrial
240 scavengers — perhaps including Pleistocene hominins²⁸ — to carcasses through their flight
241 patterns and calls, and there is strong evidence for multispecies scavenging sequences among
242 birds anchored in cross-species semiosis and co-adaptation.²⁹

243 Many human-animal interactions are likely to involve some form of interspecies
244 learning. The challenge is to describe, qualify, and differentiate these forms, and to assess their
245 short and long-term consequences for human and animal behavior alike, including their

²⁶ de Bruyn et al., “Killer Whale Ecotypes.”

²⁷ Allen and Andrews, “How Not to Find Over-Imitation in Animals.”

²⁸ Morelli et al., “The Vulture in the Sky and the Hominin on the Land.”

²⁹ Grubb et al., “Winter Scavenging of Ungulate Carrion By Bald Eagles, Common Ravens, and Coyotes In Northern Arizona.” Environmental learning can also take the form of intraspecific learning between social groups possessing different levels of experience regarding certain human-animal interactions. See, for example, Whitehead et al., “Adaptation of Sperm Whales to Open-Boat Whalers.”

246 potential integration into broader multispecies arrangements. Domestication, for example,
247 offers a model case for how humans and animals attune their behaviors to each other and
248 physiologically change in the process. This co-adaptive process does not happen in a learning
249 void but is critically facilitated by mutual understanding and co-adjusted knowledge — or
250 “zoocialization”.³⁰ Beyond domestication, a range of more specific cases illustrates how such
251 learning can be organized in different ways for different ends. Human-honeyguide relations
252 across sub-Saharan Africa involve both intra- and interspecific learning, as people adopt
253 imitated bird calls to initiate the interaction and have learned to attend to and coordinate with
254 the birds to acquire honey. Humans have learned to read the birds’ flight patterns, calls, and
255 perching choices as indications of the direction and distance to bee nests. Once a nest is located
256 and opened, humans harvest the honey and sometimes leave behind wax comb and larvae for
257 the bird.³¹ Importantly, honeyguides are nest parasites, suggesting that interactions with
258 humans result from individual learning and experimentation, rather than transmission from
259 parents to offspring.³² Some whales and dolphins have also learned to cooperate with people,
260 and this is often linked to foraging synchrony.³³ In addition, cormorant-assisted fishing has
261 long been a central livelihood practice in China and Japan, involving cross-species habituation
262 and learned behaviors in humans and their birds.³⁴

263 These few examples already indicate that learning with animals is not merely a
264 theoretical prospect but has long been important to human life, setting the scene for a dedicated
265 analysis of how environmental knowledge is *co-constructed* by humans and other animals in
266 lived interspecies praxis, involving different forms of expertise and traveling through

³⁰ Petitt and Brandt-Off, “Zoocialization.”

³¹ Wood et al., “Mutualism and Manipulation in Hadza–Honeyguide Interactions”; Spottiswoode et al., “Reciprocal Signaling in Honeyguide-Human Mutualism.”

³² Fleischer, “Ladies and Gentes.”

³³ Cantor et al., “Foraging Synchrony Drives Resilience in Human–Dolphin Mutualism.”

³⁴ Jackson, “Fishing with Cormorants”; Manzi and Coomes, “Cormorant Fishing in Southwestern China.”

267 heterogeneous networks of people, things, and animals. Calls for more inclusive research
268 epistemologies demand that we take seriously what Jamie Lorimer and Timothy Hodgetts have
269 called “more-than-human knowledge practices”.³⁵ They activate the anthropological concept
270 of multinaturalism — a perspective that not only rejects human-nature dualism but also
271 pluralizes what in European traditions has often been imagined as a singular domain of Nature,
272 positing multiple natures corresponding to different kinds of beings — to draw attention to how
273 knowledge is not a human prerogative but “possessed by nonhuman subjects, like animals,
274 plants, and even geomorphic agents like rivers”.³⁶ Such work foregrounds nonhuman beings
275 as knowers and thus encourages us to rethink anthropocentric epistemologies. Our aim here is
276 to turn the problem inside out by asking whether such more-than-human knowledge practices
277 have been operative in, or co-constitutive of, specific cultural and historical human contexts,
278 some of which may hence be better conceptualized as multispecies lifeforms.

279 The perspective developed here also creates new impetus for experimental and cultural
280 evolutionary investigations into the social transmission of knowledge: as soon as we challenge
281 the assumption that the communities of practice that constitute corresponding communities of
282 learning are human-exclusive, we can begin to unpick animal-mediated environmental learning
283 with concepts developed in these fields. We may, for example, ask what role the learning biases
284 such as the “content bias,” “model-based bias,” and “frequency-dependent bias”³⁷ have played
285 in different historical contexts. The confrontation of specific human forms of life and the
286 relevance of specific nonhuman agencies therein may already hint at the potential to generalize
287 the “context bias” of learning and social transmission.³⁸ The model-based bias is particularly
288 worth highlighting here, as it describes learning that preferentially occurs with a view to agents

³⁵ Lorimer and Hodgetts, *More-than-Human*.

³⁶ Lorimer and Hodgetts, *More-than-Human*, 12. On (perspectival) multinaturalism, see Castro, “Cosmological Deixis and Amerindian Perspectivism.”

³⁷ Mesoudi, *Cultural Evolution*; Heyes, *Cognitive Gadgets*.

³⁸ Wood et al., “Context-Dependent Model-Based Biases in Cultural Transmission.”

289 who can serve as *models* with certain characteristics and behaviors. Modalities of human
290 environmental learning that are largely oriented toward certain keystone animals might
291 conform to such a model-based bias, underscoring the point that learning theory would benefit
292 from multispecies perspectives.

293

294 **A Heuristic Typology of Animal-Mediated Environmental Learning**

295 What humans can learn from other animals and how they can learn it is neither entirely arbitrary
296 nor fully determined by supposed sets of species-level behaviors of the animals in question.
297 Environmental knowledge is negotiated under varying conditions of more-than-human praxis.
298 It is contingent upon how humans come to live together with other animals and where, when,
299 and how they interact with them in relation to their own projects and ambitions. It speaks to a
300 spectrum of degrees of proximity, reciprocity, and intensities of relations, ranging from the
301 imitation or emulation of zooalterity through various cultural practices to what might be
302 understood as more fully fledged multi- or interspecies cultures as potent learning contexts.³⁹
303 Making analytical space for how animals have influenced the learning ecologies of human
304 collectives requires a sensibility for the historical contingency and heterogeneity of interspecies
305 knowledge formation.

306

307 [Insert Figure 1 about here]

308 **Fig. 1:** Schematic representation of the three modalities of animal-mediated environmental learning.

309

³⁹ Cabral and Lähdesmäki, “Multispecies Cultures and Environmental Change”; Parker et al., “Interspecies Cultures and Future Design.”

310 To take a step toward rethinking learning from a multispecies perspective, it may be
311 useful to begin differentiating between various ways in which animals have figured in how
312 humans have made sense of particular environments. For this purpose, we propose a tripartite
313 heuristic of animal-mediated environmental learning that involves three basic modalities with
314 different levels of spatiotemporal and eco-behavioral integration (that is, how closely human
315 and animal lifeways are woven together in time, space, and patterns of activity): learning
316 *through, from, and with* animals (**Fig. 1**). This threefold scheme represents a first attempt at
317 systematizing how we might approach the multifarious involvements of other animals in
318 human environmental knowledge formation. It is neither exhaustive nor are the proposed
319 analytical categories mutually exclusive or sharply distinguished, and we will likely find that
320 they often overlap and should thus be understood as layered rather than competing descriptions.
321 Nonetheless, this typology allows us to analytically foreground different aspects of animal
322 involvement in environmental learning — for instance, whether animals primarily function as
323 observational models for humans or figure as active co-participants in joint projects. It may
324 also serve as a flexible basis for investigating related issues, such as whether modalities of
325 learning by coordination can be expanded to encompass more-than-human learning
326 ecologies.⁴⁰

327 The first modality, learning *through*, pertains to insights and inspirations gleaned from
328 animals as cultural figures (and metaphors) rather than knowledge generated through the direct
329 observation of, or interaction with, animals as ecological agents in specific environmental
330 contexts. As indicated in Figure 1, learning through is thus logically set apart from the other
331 two modalities, but it is included here both because of its broad historical and cultural relevance
332 and as a contrastive foil for our account of learning from and with animals. Unlike the latter
333 two, learning through deemphasizes animals' status as affective-embodied beings with distinct

⁴⁰ Charbonneau et al., “Flexible Cultural Learning Through Action Coordination.”

334 worldmaking capacities in specific sets of ecological relations. It thus does not fully meet what
335 we consider a key criterion of animal-mediated environmental learning proper: a receptive
336 engagement with embodied and embedded forms of zooalterity. Learning through tends to be
337 about symbolic rather than corporeal animals, who primarily function as purveyors of cultural
338 norms or moral lessons. It has, for example, helped people make sense of their place in the
339 cosmos, their roles, and responsibilities, but it tends to involve a high degree of cultural
340 impositionality in relation to its animal referents, prompting a reaffirmation rather than
341 transformation of extant cultural frameworks.

342 In mainstream Western thought, learning through animals has also tended to reduce the
343 latter to interchangeable “ciphers,” reproducing notions of human sovereignty over nature and
344 animal life.⁴¹ Thus, learning through does not refer to ways of attending to other animals based
345 on the recognition of how people are *productively different* from animals, be it as a ground for
346 cultivating and negotiating such differences or as an impetus to work toward other-than-human
347 qualities; it instead operates through anthropocentric analogies or allegories in which animals
348 appear as projections or mirrors of human ideals, virtues, or flaws. That is not to say, however,
349 that all forms of learning through are necessarily detached from actual animal presences,
350 histories, and lifeways. Coyote, an ambivalent trickster and creator figure in many North
351 American Indigenous traditions, may be a case in point. Coyote’s central cultural role may have
352 some historical grounding in the animal’s ecological biography and status as a “consummate
353 survivor in a shifting world,” who may have drawn human attention for enduring the climatic
354 changes and megafaunal extinctions of the late Pleistocene and — as a highly social predator
355 — invited identification on the part of human hunters, suggesting a symbolic codification of
356 an original responsiveness to animal alterity.⁴²

⁴¹ Tyler, *Ciferae*.

⁴² Hyde, *Trickster Makes This World*, 43; Flores, *Coyote America*, 28–29.

357 Learning *from* other animals prioritizes engaging with animals as ecological agents and
358 occurs when people look to animals as models for how to be active in the world, as sources of
359 information, skills, or tools. Animals in this modality will often exemplify what kind of insights
360 may be gained by embracing specific perspectives on a shared environment: they illustrate
361 what can be done and known by mobilizing specific bodies and perceptive registers. Learning
362 from animals will thus involve strategies of mimesis, simulation, impersonation, and re-
363 enactment, and typically requires some form of transfer or translation. An interesting case of
364 this is animal self-medication, a phenomenon observable in a diversity of species from
365 honeybees to spider monkeys that has spawned its own area of multidisciplinary study,
366 zoopharmacognosy or “animal knowledge of medicine”.⁴³ Already in Aristotle we find reports
367 of animals using plants to treat illness, repel parasites, neutralize poisons, or heal wounds, and
368 both European folklore and TEK harbor a rich panoply of evidence that people have long turned
369 to animals to gain medicinal knowledge.⁴⁴ Traditional tracking practices can also be seen as
370 products of animal-mediated landscape learning, helping people navigate their environment,
371 find specific locales and landforms (such as water holes and islands), access particular animal
372 and vegetal resources, and generally shape landscape perception and conceptualization in
373 significant ways.⁴⁵

374 However, it is the third modality — learning *with* animals — that we are particularly
375 interested in here and wish to explore in more detail. This modality moves beyond isolated
376 instances of observation or borrowing through transfer or translation onto sustained
377 interactions, typically bound to modes of multispecies dwelling that foster landscape sharing
378 and provide openings for animal neighborhoods. Learning with animals thus designates a

⁴³ Rodriguez and Wrangham, “Zoopharmacognosy”; Huffman, “Animal Self-Medication and Ethno-Medicine.”

⁴⁴ Huffman, “Folklore, Animal Self-Medication, and Phytotherapy—Something Old, Something New, Something Borrowed, Some Things True.”

⁴⁵ Pastoors and Lenssen-Erz, *Reading Prehistoric Human Tracks*; du Plessis, “Tracking Meat of the Sand.”

379 broader set of conditions in which human action and thought in and about particular landscapes
380 are formed within, and depend upon, human-animal co-ecologies.⁴⁶ Such knowledge formation
381 is deeply embedded in patterns of co-existence and relies on a convergence of human and
382 animal lifeways, so that the conduct of animal life can serve as a potent context to develop or
383 inspire ways of acting and thinking in these landscapes. Learning with animals in this sense is
384 most likely to attest to their congeniality, autonomy, and agency as they enter human practices
385 as ecological guides and teachers. It is the most subtle and complex modality, as the sort of
386 environmental insights proffered will emerge from how humans and other animals *come to*
387 *cohabit* their landscapes. Such learning will rely on animal-informed rhythms, perspectives,
388 proclivities, and sometimes materialities, but it will almost always promote some kind of eco-
389 behavioral familiarization or attunement.

390 Learning with animals can be understood as a consequence of human “relevance
391 realization” in specific human-animal systems, insofar as the agency of humans as biocultural
392 organisms is both grounded in and responsive to those more-than-human aspects of the
393 environment that are deemed relevant in a given context. Like other creatures, humans, too,
394 must selectively transform “ill-defined problems into well-defined ones,” large worlds into
395 smaller, meaningful ones that afford concrete action.⁴⁷ This relevance is not pre-given but
396 relational, and so the intriguing question is which animal others inform human dwelling in
397 which societal and environmental configurations, and in what ways. To the extent that *learning*
398 with and *living* with other animals are deeply integrated processes, individual aspects of the
399 former may be challenging to disentangle analytically from the broader cluster of interspecies
400 relations. We should note that we do not make a general distinction between learning with
401 animals and their instrumental use here, although distinctions of this kind may crystallize

⁴⁶ See e.g. Fuentes, “Naturalcultural Encounters in Bali.”

⁴⁷ Jaeger et al., “Naturalizing Relevance Realization,” 2.

402 empirically when looking at specific cases. Rather, our operative assumption is that what
403 Donna Haraway has termed “relations of use” may often also be relations of learning, as long
404 as people attend and adjust to animal capacities.⁴⁸ The key point about learning with animals
405 is not symmetry but the co-enabling character of specific multispecies arrangements, and the
406 kind of action spaces that specific beings and lifeways can open up for each other. This can be
407 formulated as a question of affordances: what are the affording qualities of the ways animals
408 use and inhabit landscapes for the people who share those landscapes with them?⁴⁹

409

410 **Learning Environments with Other Animals**

411 Early Holocene beavers in northern Europe provide a good example of such affording quality.
412 Beavers have long been argued to have prepared and “nursed” these landscapes at the end of
413 the Ice Age, facilitating the return of human foragers to higher European latitudes.⁵⁰ The
414 available (zoo-)archaeological evidence suggests that beaver niche construction and ecosystem
415 engineering supplied foundational environmental affordances drawn upon by Mesolithic and
416 Neolithic foraging societies (c. 10,000–4,000 years ago).⁵¹ A macro-scale analysis of the pan-
417 European north indicates that these human societies oriented their foraging behaviors toward
418 the mammal and fish species promoted in beaver-sustained wetlands, gathered reptiles and
419 water plants benefitting from beaver pond-building, and relied on the rich avian communities
420 (especially waterbirds) sustained by biodiversity-fostering beaver landscapes. In northwestern
421 and even more so in northeastern Europe, Mesolithic societies acquired beaver teeth and near-
422 complete mandibles and employed them as tools.⁵² Strikingly, these beaver-sourced tools were

⁴⁸ Haraway, *When Species Meet*, chap. 3.

⁴⁹ Hussain, “Deep Animal Prehistory.”

⁵⁰ Coles, *Beavers in Britain's Past*; Liarsou, “Interactions between the Beaver (*Castor Fiber L.*) and Human Societies”; Hjørungdal, “Reaching Them a Human Paw.”

⁵¹ Hussain and Brusgaard, “Human-Beaver Cohabitation.”

⁵² See Schmölcke, Groß, and Nikulina, “Bears and Beavers”; Zhilin, “Beaver Mandible Tools.”

423 often minimally modified yet maintained and resharpened, undermining their interpretation as
424 mere “ad hoc” instruments. Moreover, their modes of instrumentalization closely mirror the
425 original role of the associated beaver body-parts,⁵³ suggesting that specific “beaver
426 functionalities” exemplifying the environmental agency of these animals were *borrowed*, albeit
427 slightly adjusted and thereby “translated,” into the domain of human action.⁵⁴ All of this
428 suggests that beavers galvanized an entire way of life for their human neighbors and helped
429 motivate these humans to live in and interact with their environments in particular ways. While
430 practices of selective borrowing and translation may also exemplify human learning *from*
431 beavers, the more salient point for us is that the attention to beaver others emerged from multi-
432 millennial human-beaver wetland co-dwelling which, in turn, reconfigures human foraging
433 strategies, mobility patterns, and material culture.

434 Human-bear relations promise to disclose complementary patterns of animal-mediated
435 environmental learning. Owing to their pronounced ecological and dietary plasticity, bears have
436 often been among the pioneer species to occupy novel environments and thus to have served
437 as other-than-human model organisms, teaching humans how to inhabit, and survive in, these
438 environments. An interesting candidate context for this is the Dorset period of the Canadian
439 Arctic and Greenland (c. 2,500–800 years ago). Like their pre-Dorset precursors, Dorset
440 foragers predominantly targeted subadult seals close to the edge of the sea ice, a strategy
441 bearing striking echoes of polar bear seal-hunting behavior.⁵⁵ In addition, polar bears form the
442 most significant theme in carved zoomorphic art and visual culture, second only to human
443 depictions. These bear renderings are overtly “representational” in that they reproduce the
444 postures and movements most characteristic of seal-hunting polar bears and emphasize the
445 body features — notably heads and limbs — most important in these activities. Indeed, the

⁵³ Zhilin, “Beaver Mandible Tools.”

⁵⁴ Hussain and Brusgaard, “Human-Beaver Cohabitation.”

⁵⁵ Murray, “Prehistoric Use of Ringed Seals.”

446 proportionality of bear representations along these dimensions of “being-an-ursid-seal-hunter”
447 correlates closely with the distributional frequencies of such behavior among contemporary
448 seal-hunting polar bears.⁵⁶ Matthew Betts and colleagues have argued that Dorset seal-hunting
449 technology has been adapted to still-standing lurking/stalking, the same hunting habitus most
450 frequently adopted by bears and most abundantly visualized in the art, suggesting a close
451 alignment between Dorset hunting practice, bear hunting behavior, and bear-centered visual
452 culture as a medium of animal-mediated environmental learning.

453 The first people who came into the Canadian Arctic may have thus learned to live along
454 the ice from polar bear others, the original inhabitants of these landscapes. To thrive there,
455 people observed and emulated bears and translated what they learned into their lifestyle and
456 material culture. The fact that Dorset bear representations become more frequent in the
457 archaeological record over time supports this interpretation⁵⁷ as the respective bear-related
458 knowledge was codified in material culture — a constant reminder that in order to be Dorset
459 one needed to be, or needed to “aspire to be,” bear and act bear-like in the Arctic
460 environment.⁵⁸ This idea of human-bear ecological kinship may have been further elaborated
461 through practices of materially harnessing bear perspectives and capacities, visually evoking
462 human-bear hybrids, and manufacturing artefacts with joint human and bear counterparts.
463 Dorset longhouses — large communal structures — have been suggested to be architectural
464 recreations of “bear-ness,” spatial representations of a bear’s spine and head and its axial
465 skeleton,⁵⁹ an idea supported by depositions of polar bear bones from the same body parts in
466 the axial extremities of some of these longhouses.⁶⁰ Dorset therefore registers a pervasive “bear
467 logic”: bear behaviors, capacities, and interpositions with humans appear to anchor much of its

⁵⁶ Betts et al., “How Animals Create Human History.”

⁵⁷ Hardenberg, *Trends and Ontology of Artistic Practices of the Dorset Culture 800 BC-1300 AD*.

⁵⁸ Betts, Hardenberg, and Stirling, p. 107.

⁵⁹ Plumet, “Le Foyer Dans l’Arctique.”

⁶⁰ Damkjar, “Late Dorset Longhouses.”

468 archaeological record, suggesting that inhabiting the landscape for Dorset people often meant
469 matching perspectives with the bears and heeding bear-mediated knowledge.

470 After the glaciers had retreated at the end of the last Ice Age, beached large baleen
471 whales such as bowheads and ice-trapped belugas were likely a key factor sustaining the
472 earliest human excursions into the far north of southern Scandinavia, the virgin extension of
473 the eastern North Atlantic ocean today known as the Skagerrak-Kattegat seaboard.⁶¹ Among
474 the few carnivores represented in the pioneer assemblages of northern Jutland, where the
475 Skagerrak and Kattegat meet, are brown and polar bears, dated to a warm phase during the Late
476 Glacial period — the Allerød interstadial (c. 13,300-12,800 years ago)⁶² — the same timeframe
477 the earliest forager material culture is presently attributed to.⁶³ Modern Arctic polar bears in
478 coastal regions known to periodically rely on stranded whales, especially during warmer stages
479 when the sea ice shrinks and seal availability is reduced,⁶⁴ and it has also been suggested that
480 bears might have been key to the early navigation of the unfamiliar landscapes of northern
481 Jutland. Together with the seabirds rapidly aggregating at whale carcasses, bears acted as
482 beacons, drawing human attention to stranding sites, occasionally excavating frozen whales,
483 and locating and preying on smaller whales such as belugas trapped by the ice, thereby making
484 otherwise hard-to-detect resources environmentally salient for human foragers.⁶⁵
485 Consequently, in the context of early human dispersal into such landscapes, bears might have
486 helped orient human behaviors by pointing to relevant resources, locales, and ecosystem
487 dynamics, with bear agency becoming an exemplar for human action and cognition. Emerging

⁶¹ Hussain et al., “Was the Late Glacial Human Occupation of Northernmost Europe Facilitated by Whales?”

⁶² Aaris-Sørensen, *Diversity and Dynamics of the Mammalian Fauna in Denmark throughout the Last Glacial-Interglacial Cycle, 115-0 Kyr BP*, 18.

⁶³ Hussain et al., “Was the Late Glacial Human Occupation of Northernmost Europe Facilitated by Whales?”

⁶⁴ Laidre et al., “Historical and Potential Future Importance of Large Whales as Food for Polar Bears.”

⁶⁵ Hussain, “The Heath and the Sea”; Heide-Jørgensen et al., “Three Recent Ice Entrapments of Arctic Cetaceans in West Greenland and the Eastern Canadian High Arctic” for recent analogs of beluga sea-ice trappings.

488 biomolecular evidence from recovered stone tools supports this general scenario, notably
489 pointing to human-bear convergences vis-à-vis beluga whale exploitation.⁶⁶

490 When co-inhabiting landscapes with people, bears have frequently been among the
491 “cultural keystone species”⁶⁷ of Indigenous societies around the world, yet they often remain
492 relatively invisible in their material and visual cultures. This may offer an important reminder
493 for investigating the role of animals in human learning. When people learn the specificities of
494 their environments with animals, the latter are the embodied referents of such learning, and the
495 relationship is observational, lived, and direct — the target is the empirical other as a sentient
496 being. Yet human-bear relations negotiated through material and visual practices may involve
497 bears as a *substitute* for such lived engagements, and, as such, may flag culturally derived
498 interstices decoupled from experience or at least integrating such ecological knowledge *post*
499 *hoc* into broader worldviews and normative registers, shifting animal-mediated learning from
500 immediate co-presence to a more detached, symbolic and abstract register. This inherent
501 tension, in turn, may indeed help explain why bears rarely show up as depicted animals in the
502 archaeological record and why engagement with bear materiality and visibility often increases
503 with more advanced regional settlement histories.⁶⁸

504 Eurocentric perspectives on the deep-time processes of dog domestication similarly
505 tend to overlook significant opportunities for mutual learning and co-adaptation that
506 undergirded incipient human-wolf relationships.⁶⁹ The oral history and cultural memory of
507 North American peoples from the Great Plains and Intermountain West suggest that the human-
508 initiation model of Pleistocene dog domestication (in both of its variants, the “scavenger

⁶⁶ Blood serum analysis of a sample of stone tools from the Hollendskær area of northern Jutland has yielded preliminary evidence of 1-2 residual blood signatures of beluga whales (unpublished data).

⁶⁷ Clark et al., “Grizzly and Polar Bears as Nonconsumptive Cultural Keystone Species.”

⁶⁸ This is reflected not only in the Dorset case but also in the Mesolithic-Neolithic-Bronze Age sequence of hunter-gatherer-fisher societies of the East European plain forest zone. See Kashina and Khramtsova, “In the Company of Bears.”

⁶⁹ Fogg et al., “Relationships between Indigenous American Peoples and Wolves 1.”

509 hypothesis” and the “cross-species adoption hypothesis”⁷⁰) requires critical re-evaluation, as
510 wolves are conceptualized as potent guides and key nonhumans who taught humans how to
511 navigate and sustain themselves in their environments. Lupines conspicuously feature as
512 “tutors” and “instructors” from whom people learned how to hunt when they first arrived in
513 North America.⁷¹ Indigenous accounts not only suggest that people observed wolves and then
514 adopted some of their hunting techniques such as driving prey off cliffs, into ravines, or into
515 deep snow,⁷² they also point to important behavioral complementarities between the two
516 species that would have encouraged interspecies synchronization and perhaps even
517 cooperation: wolves have the ability to more easily stalk, pursue, corner, and exhaust large prey
518 animals such as elk, bison, or mastodon yet often face difficulties killing them, while the human
519 foragers tool-assisted lifestyle likely made them more suited to this task.⁷³ Even “optimal
520 foraging” accounts must consider interspecies cooperation under such conditions: “humans
521 would have avoided costly pursuits and wolves would have avoided injuries sustained while
522 killing dangerous prey”.⁷⁴

523 The large-scale funneling landscapes with “bison drive architecture” Indigenous North
524 Americans began to devise and maintain from at least 13,000 years ago onward⁷⁵ — and the
525 distinct affordances for sociopolitical organization that came with them — may have thus been
526 inspired by wolf-derived knowledge. Practices of sharing meat with wolves that have persisted
527 to this day also support an original context of collaborative hunting.⁷⁶ Carcass sharing and
528 defense are indeed an important yet often neglected means of negotiating and reinforcing

⁷⁰ Serpell, “Commensalism or Cross-Species Adoption?”

⁷¹ Fogg et al., “Relationships between Indigenous American Peoples and Wolves 1”; Pierotti and Fogg, *The First Domestication*.

⁷² Barsh and Marlor, “Driving Bison and Blackfoot Science.”

⁷³ Cram et al., “Ecology and Evolution of Human-Wildlife Cooperation”; Shipman, *The Invaders*.

⁷⁴ Cram et al., “The Ecology and Evolution of Human-Wildlife Cooperation.” 845.

⁷⁵ Speth, “13,000 Years of Communal Bison Hunting in Western North America.”

⁷⁶ Pierotti and Fogg, *The First Domestication*.

529 interspecies bonds⁷⁷ — and, following Kimmerer, these practices were likely integral to a
530 broader “economy of gifts and abundance” in which sharing, respect, gratitude, and reciprocity
531 extended into the nonhuman realm.⁷⁸ Indigenous human-bison relationships may have also
532 been a product of wolf attunement and wolf-oriented landscape learning, emerging from efforts
533 to coordinate and broker human and wolf neighborhoods. As Barsh and Marlor note,
534 “[Blackfoot could have adopted] a deductive, ‘scientific’ approach. Or they could have
535 observed wolves, recognized the usefulness of wolves’ knowledge, and then imitated wolves’
536 behavior to insert themselves into the existing bison–wolf relationship without significantly
537 changing it. Blackfoot today report that they followed this ‘empathetic’ approach. Instead of
538 collecting data on bison, Blackfoot performed wolves.”⁷⁹

539 Irrespective of whether people and bison were initially drawn together by wolf agency
540 (and answers may differ across contexts), sustained cohabitation with bison populations opened
541 up another set of distinct learning opportunities. There is significant geographic and temporal
542 overlap between the presence of bison, the extent of a prairie-woodland mosaic, and
543 anthropogenic fire practices throughout the Holocene in northeastern North America. The area
544 also broadly overlaps with the region in which early evidence for plant management and
545 cultivation has been recorded, including the so-called Eastern Agricultural Complex of the mid-
546 Holocene. By considering bison ecology and ecological engineering and conducting controlled
547 field experiments in the Joseph H. Williams Tallgrass Prairie Preserve, which is grazed by
548 around 2500 bison, Natalie Mueller and colleagues have demonstrated that bison agency,
549 promoted by regular low-level burning, creates distinctive pockets of early-succession
550 vegetation (often in edge habitats, adjacent to bison trails, or in bison wallows) and that such
551 pockets uniquely support progenitor crop species and other edible plants, including species

⁷⁷ Nadasdy, “The Gift in the Animal.”

⁷⁸ Kimmerer, *The Serviceberry*, 78, 105.

⁷⁹ Barsh and Marlor, “Driving Bison and Blackfoot Science,” 585.

552 such as little barley, mayflower, and sumpweed.⁸⁰ Moreover, dense clusters of crop progenitors
553 in these experimental settings assumed “the appearance of fields”.⁸¹ As people traversed bison
554 landscapes following bison tracks, living with and being attentive to bison others would thus
555 have provided a compelling context for learning to manipulate and manage plants for human
556 sustenance and quite literally *modeled* field-tending dynamics. Bison affordances may hence
557 point to a hitherto neglected context of discovery and impetus for innovation regarding the
558 emergence of human agroecologies, offering an alternative perspective on the early
559 development of “agricultural” practices and challenging classic “Neolithic revolution”
560 narratives with their Euro- and anthropocentric legacies.⁸²

561 This also discloses a broader perspective on some of the relevant learning contexts
562 contributing to the portfolio of human interventions with the world of plants. The majority of
563 the wild ancestors of the small-seeded species of herbaceous annuals cultivated in the mid-
564 Holocene (such as millet, quinoa, and buckwheat) were facilitated by the activities of grazing
565 megafauna, who dispersed and promoted them in the landscape in a way that humans could
566 easily emulate and eventually overtake megafaunal functions like seed dispersal. In doing so,
567 humans initiated a trajectory of human-plant coevolution which in many cases would lead to
568 plant cultivation.⁸³ Based on a review of ethnographic data on pastoralist socioecological
569 systems in the Americas, Lezama-Núñez et al. trace how “Old World” herbivore introductions
570 in the 15th to 16th centuries engendered entirely “novel uses of the local flora” and associated
571 human lifeways, in some cases encouraging previously unrecorded plant management practices
572 and human selection of plant phenotypes.⁸⁴ Navajo livestock corrals, for example — the core
573 of Navajo livelihoods since the 19th century — have promoted unique pioneer vegetation

⁸⁰ Mueller et al., “Bison, Anthropogenic Fire, and the Origins of Agriculture.”

⁸¹ Mueller et al., “Bison, Anthropogenic Fire, and the Origins of Agriculture,” 154.

⁸² Swanson et al., *Domestication Gone Wild*.

⁸³ Spengler and Mueller, “Grazing Animals Drove Domestication of Grain Crops.”

⁸⁴ Lezama-Núñez et al., “Herding Ecologies and Ongoing Plant Domestication Processes in the Americas.”

574 through sheep, cattle, and horse grazing, strongly overlapping with a sizable range of traditional
575 Navajo food plants such as beeweed, knotweed, and mustards.⁸⁵ The integration of these plants
576 into human lifeways, in this case, is neither strictly human- nor animal-initiated but instead
577 emerges from shared multispecies life. The same plant-animal-human relationships are
578 codified in Navajo cosmovisions, in which sheep figure as “carriers” and “consignors” of
579 valuable plants.

580 In a related historical and geographical context, the reshaping of Indigenous life in the
581 North American grasslands through human-horse entanglements in the 18th century can then
582 be understood in part as the product of a novel equine-mediated affordance landscape, the
583 transformation of the Great Plains into a dynamic space of unprecedented mobility accessed
584 and maintained through the capabilities of equine bodies. Horse metabolisms made the
585 generous amounts of photosynthetic energy stored in the grasslands available for human use,
586 yet they also changed “the meanings of the land — what people saw when they looked at the
587 country and imagined its future”.⁸⁶ The potential that came with rearranging human modalities
588 of existence around equines was recognized both by longstanding inhabitants of the grasslands,
589 such as the Blackfoot, and by latecomers like the Comanche and Cheyenne. Historians have
590 pointed to the enormous sociocultural, ecological, and political consequences of the widespread
591 transition to equestrian nomadism.⁸⁷ The central role of horses not only required (as noted by
592 John C. Ewers) the “learning of new motor habits” and “specialized manual skills”⁸⁸ such as
593 hobbling, picketing, or corralling, it also meant that the equines themselves functioned as
594 conduits of new forms of environmental knowledge that provided the basis of the human-horse

⁸⁵ Kuznar, “Ecological Mutualism in Navajo Corrals.”

⁸⁶ West, *The Contested Plains*, 54.

⁸⁷ West, *The Contested Plains*; Ewers, *The Horse in Blackfoot Indian Culture*; Roe, *The Indian and the Horse*; Hämäläinen, “The Rise and Fall of Plains Indian Horse Cultures”; Mitchell, *Horse Nations*, chaps. 4–6; Bethke, “Revisiting the Horse in Blackfoot Culture.”

⁸⁸ Ewers, *The Horse in Blackfoot Indian Culture*, 301.

595 entanglements that came to dominate life on the Plains in the 18th and 19th centuries. The bison
596 economy had drawn Native peoples onto the prairies, and an understanding of bison behavior
597 depended in part on an understanding of the grasslands' defining environmental feature: the
598 grass itself. Yet it was arguably only when Plains equestrians developed from mounted bison
599 hunters into bison-hunting horse pastoralists who inhabited the grasslands year-round with
600 often sizeable herds of equines that they came to view and manage these prairie landscapes as
601 a complex mosaic of grazing areas and water sources in a way that reflected a distinctly equine-
602 mediated and equine-centered "relearning" of the grasslands *as* grasslands in a more
603 comprehensive sense than (was necessary) before. In this process, the horse gradually emerged
604 as a kind of nonhuman benchmark and model system for inhabiting and acting in the Plains
605 environment.

606 Consequently, the idea of Plains Indian "horse cultures" needs to be conceptualized
607 beyond the mere use of horses as tools of mobility and warfare or markers of social status and
608 economic wealth, encompassing essential learning and decision-making processes that
609 emerged from the observation of, and interaction with, horses as embodied ecological agents.
610 To a significant extent, learning with horses consisted of the adaptation of traditional
611 ethnobotanical knowledge as knowledge of grassland topography and ecology was modified to
612 account for equine foraging patterns and grazing preferences and the distribution, accessibility,
613 quality, and seasonal cycles of prairie grasses, from the bluestem grasses abundant in the
614 tallgrass prairie and mixed-grass ecotone to the grama and buffalograss of the drier shortgrass
615 prairie, some of which grew in distinct plant communities.⁸⁹ Attending to how horses
616 maintained weight or declined on particular pastures, how quickly grazed areas recovered, and
617 where animals chose (or refused) to graze might have offered indications of soil and forage
618 quality not legible to human observers alone. This may be understood in terms of specific

⁸⁹ Savage, *Prairie*; Sherow, *The Grasslands of the United States*.

619 “somatic modes of attention,” in which human bodily awareness was trained on equine bodies
620 and movements as vehicles of environmental information.⁹⁰

621 Paying attention to the meanings of equine movement across the landscape and
622 developing an eye for subtle differences in vegetation that perhaps went unnoticed during what
623 Ewers called the “Pedestrian Culture Period” were interconnected dimensions of
624 environmental learning that became increasingly important with the rise of horse pastoralism.
625 Horses did thus not simply extend human reach: their bodily responses to grassland
626 environments became a medium through which people could refine and recalibrate their
627 understandings of the grasslands as a differentiated ecological field, bringing into view a mode
628 of learning fostered through human-equid coupling.

629 Plains Indians also learned to accommodate the specifics of equine grazing behavior
630 and “horse perspectives” into their patterns of nomadic mobility and land use. Being selective
631 grazers, horses tended to move on to other grazing areas rather than resort to grasses of inferior
632 quality (from their point of view) once the desirable grass in an area had been depleted, and
633 Plains people quickly learned that grazing horses wandering out of sight of the camp were a
634 clear indicator of the need to relocate. Securing nutritious winter pasturage was a significant
635 issue that was addressed by splitting up into smaller bands and spending the cold season in
636 riverine or riparian microenvironments where stretches of grass continued to be available and
637 horses could be fed with cottonwood bark when grass became scarce.⁹¹ Piegan Blackfoot elders
638 interviewed by Ewers in the 1940s informed him that their preference for wintering along
639 Montana’s Marias River came to be because they observed that it contained a variety of grasses
640 liked by their horses.⁹² In Rockman’s terms, both “locational” and “limitational” environmental

⁹⁰ Csordas, “Somatic Modes of Attention.”

⁹¹ Ewers, *The Horse in Blackfoot Indian Culture*, 40–44; West, *The Way to the West*, chap. 1; Sherow, “Workings of the Geodialectic”; Moore, *The Cheyenne Nation*, chap. 5; Osborn, “Ecological Aspects of Equestrian Adaptations in Aboriginal North America.”

⁹² LaPier, *Invisible Reality*, 58–59.

641 knowledge among horse pastoralists spoke to, and helped sustain, the reality of deepening
642 human-horse entanglements that defined Plains horse pastoralism and the concomitant
643 interplay of human and horse (or human-horse) agency and vulnerability within a specific set
644 of socioecological parameters.⁹³

645 At this point, we should caution against reading an implicit normativity into both the
646 general idea of learning with other animals and the examples given here, in the sense that this
647 modality of environmental learning might seem to offer a prescriptive “model” for an ethics of
648 multispecies conviviality, speaking to broader attempts at overcoming entrenched regimes of
649 destructive anthropocentric exploitation. It is important, therefore, to be wary of an
650 “Anthropocene presentism” that frames how we look at (all) animal-mediated environmental
651 learning — as a blanket alternative to anthropocentric power dynamics, as an inherently
652 emancipatory process, or as an unambiguous ecological or ethical good. In principle,
653 environmental learning — or its downstream effects and implication in broader processes of
654 social and ecological transformation — can support both convivial and coercive configurations
655 of life as well as a vast space of ambiguity in between. Plains horse cultures might themselves
656 serve as an example for this, since the new forms of mobility and subsistence (and resistance)
657 enabled by equestrianism and rapidly growing horse herds not only contributed to the
658 ecological decline of the grasslands but also led to increased warfare and social stratification
659 through concentrations of equine wealth among a small circle of male elites.⁹⁴

660 The histories of settler colonialism might similarly bring into view a darker side of the
661 phenomenon: cases in which animal-mediated environmental learning was more directly
662 entangled with, or even actively employed for, projects of domination. If we understand settler
663 colonialism as a multispecies phenomenon that saw European settlers mobilize (with varying

⁹³ Rockman, “Knowledge and Learning in the Archaeology of Colonization.”

⁹⁴ See Hämäläinen, “The Rise and Fall of Plains Indian Horse Cultures.”

664 degrees of purposeful directedness) the biological capacities, behavioral specificities, and
665 ecological impacts of the organisms they brought with them, and surrounded themselves with,
666 then settler environmental learning can be investigated as the historically situated ways in
667 which settlers came to observe, interpret, and strategically recalibrate these dynamics in order
668 to remake landscapes in their own image. In this context, European domesticates have been
669 variously discussed as creatures or proxies of empire or as “shock troops” of expanding settler
670 collectives, with cattle and sheep having assumed important roles as colonial landscape and
671 ecosystem engineers who helped create conditions of habitability that fit settler socioeconomic
672 and cultural needs.⁹⁵ We might ask to what extent such roles emerged automatically from the
673 mere presence of these animals, and to what extent they were instead shaped by
674 self-consciously articulated settler understandings. As Norbert Finzsch has argued in the
675 Australian context, instead of fostering ecological resilience, environmental learning may well
676 be a driving force behind ecocidal processes, not least if contested modalities of land use and
677 inhabitation are accompanied by highly asymmetrical power relations. Finzsch underscores
678 that at least some Australian settlers were not only quite aware of the socioecological intricacies
679 that shaped Australian landscapes, native fauna, and Aboriginal people — specifically the
680 interdependencies between traditional fire management, open grasslands, kangaroo
681 populations, and Aboriginal livelihoods — they also saw how their own land use practices —
682 specifically the introduction of cattle and the concomitant expansion of grazing — advanced
683 what the settler populace conveniently understood as an inevitable “extinction” of Indigenous
684 life in the face of European “civilization”.⁹⁶ While a more detailed discussion of this issue is
685 beyond the scope of this article, it is thus worth investigating how far such ecological outcomes

⁹⁵ Anderson, *Creatures of Empire*; Dale, “Empire’s Proxy”; Milton, “The Transvaal Beef Frontier,” 200; Ohrem, “Human-Animal Relations and the Ontopolitics of Civilization.”

⁹⁶ Finzsch, “The Intrusion Therefore of Cattle Is by Itself Sufficient to Produce the Extirpation of the Native Race.” On kangaroos in Aboriginal and settler contexts, see Gelder and Weaver, *Colonial Kangaroo Hunt*; Telfer and Garde, “Indigenous Knowledge of Rock Kangaroo Ecology.”

686 can be traced to identifiable instances of environmental learning through which settlers
687 selectively incorporated and repurposed knowledge about local ecologies in ways that furthered
688 colonial projects.

689

690 **Conclusion**

691 The problem of knowledge has been increasingly pluralized, as a multiplicity of “ways of
692 knowing” are now being recognized as crucial to the operation of both society and science⁹⁷
693 and as alternative cognitive and practical resources for tackling a planetary polycrisis
694 intricately interwoven in its historical genesis with dominant (and destructive) epistemologies
695 and forms of knowledge.⁹⁸ Knowledge production has been disaggregated and shown to be
696 more messy, multifarious, and distributed than traditional accounts have been willing to admit,
697 with significant implications not only for what knowledge *is* but also for where it resides and
698 what agencies take part in its creation and propagation. The plurivocality of human knowing is
699 increasingly viewed as a value in itself, and there is growing recognition that coming to know
700 the world in human terms is also a matter of justice, insofar as different forms of human life
701 articulate and depend on different forms of knowing. Knowledge shapes and is shaped by
702 human actions, needs, and imaginative horizons, and is thus a fundamental legacy of the
703 attempts of human societies to make themselves at home in their environments, including the
704 diverse nonhumans engaged in this way. This diversity of human knowing is an integral part
705 of our species-level heritage. But as we have argued in this article, making adequate sense of
706 this heritage benefits from, and indeed often requires, a multispecies perspective.

⁹⁷ Kellert et al., *Scientific Pluralism*; Cat, “Essay Review.”

⁹⁸ Frank et al., *The Blind Spot*.

707 Human knowledge gestures beyond the human and therefore requires attention to the
708 ways in which it is *historically* configured in, and through, specific more-than-human
709 entanglements. This includes a consideration of nonhuman model organisms who may provide
710 shortcuts to relevant elements of know-that and know-how especially in scenarios of elevated
711 environmental novelty exposure (whether produced by environmental change or human
712 agency). We hope that the examples we have sketched here underscore that specific nonhuman
713 modalities of life within broader multispecies assemblages can disclose potent learning
714 contexts for human communities that address specific human needs and tie in with specific
715 human practices and lifeways, commonly organized (for lack of better concepts) around broad
716 categories such as terrestrial foragers, marine collectors, pastoralists, horticulturalists, farmers,
717 and so forth. From human-honeyguide collaboration in African savannas via Arctic seal hunters
718 attuning their practices and built environments to polar bear ways of being to the
719 equine-mediated “relearning” of the North American grasslands — the key point we have tried
720 to convey here is that the historical and archaeological records hold alternative interpretations
721 and neglected perspectives on how humans have come to know, differentiate, and rework
722 environments through sustained engagements with other animals’ bodies, behaviors, and
723 ecological relationships. Taken together, the examples of animal-mediated environmental
724 learning discussed here thus point to a “didactic opening to animal alterity” as a consequential
725 force in human history and a central characteristic of human worldmaking.⁹⁹

726 Paying attention to how nonhuman beings have co-configured processes of human
727 environmental learning helps dismantle “species island” models of behavior and cognition and
728 may provide additional grounding for perspectives on multispecies societies or (co-)cultures.¹⁰⁰
729 Horizontal interspecies learning dynamics may indeed offer a mechanism for more-than-

⁹⁹ Marchesini, “The Theriosphere,” 119.

¹⁰⁰ Cabral and Lähdesmäki, “Multispecies Cultures and Environmental Change”; Andrews et al., “Multi-Species Societies.”; Sueur and Huffman, “Co-Cultures.”

730 human history broadly comparable to the principle of horizontal gene transfer in evolutionary
731 biology, and we argue that its transformative potential may be no less significant.¹⁰¹ In this
732 regard, it can be useful to think of such interspecies learning as a form of situated modelling in
733 which the physical, behavioral, and cognitive features of an organism's *Umwelt* are sieved and
734 represented in terms of their relevance and affording qualities for the organism in question,
735 with key animal others emerging as model systems for habituation.¹⁰² As "inferential
736 blueprints,"¹⁰³ models of the situated environment allow organisms to learn this environment
737 without cognitive overload, yet who or what counts as a (key) agent within these models
738 remains an open question that demands historical specificity.

739 We suggest that a focus on animal-mediated environmental learning allows for a fruitful
740 broadening of current learning theory by attending to "heterospecific" or "hybrid" communities
741 of learners.¹⁰⁴ To make some initial sense of the diversity of animal-mediated learning
742 dynamics, we have proposed a heuristic distinction between three kinds of environmental
743 learning: learning *through*, learning *from*, and learning *with* animals. Most of our examples
744 have dealt with the latter category, as this form of embedded learning by means of extended
745 co-existence is arguably most easily overlooked when standard learning categories —
746 including those from cultural evolutionary learning theory¹⁰⁵ — are employed to study
747 interspecies dynamics. We have identified learning with animals as the most complex modality
748 of animal-mediated learning: it is expected to be less concretized (for example, through isolated
749 focal animal-mimicking practices or specific material artefacts) and will often revolve around
750 animal-oriented action coordination and broader convergences of human and animal life.

¹⁰¹ Soucy et al., "Horizontal Gene Transfer."

¹⁰² Jaeger et al., "Naturalizing Relevance Realization"; Kockelman, "Biosemiosis, Technocognition, and Sociogenesis."

¹⁰³ Massimi, *Perspectival Realism*.

¹⁰⁴ Marchesini, "The Theriosphere," 117; Lestel, "Hybrid Communities."

¹⁰⁵ Shennan, *Genes, Memes and Human History*; Eerkens and Lipo, "Cultural Transmission Theory and the Archaeological Record."

751 Importantly, the three modalities proposed here are not intended to be ontologically discrete or
752 even mutually exclusive kinds of animal-mediated learning but rather analytical lenses that
753 allow us to foreground different aspects of more-than-human learning ecologies. Concrete
754 historical situations will often involve more than one modality, and different modalities will
755 assume different degrees of salience or centrality. Which configurations matter in any given
756 case will have to be established empirically on a case-by-case basis, and it will also depend on
757 the kinds of questions asked and scales of analysis adopted.

758 Grappling with these issues of human environmental learning holds much
759 contemporary relevance — after all, the Anthropocene predicament, according to many,
760 involves our “alienation” from nature, and our inability to learn *with* nature instead of against
761 it. “An important aspect of our current dilemma,” notes anthropologist Emilio Moran, “is the
762 grasping under what conditions human populations learn and adapt to their environment.”¹⁰⁶
763 One response to the diagnosis of the escalating polycrisis has been a clarion call for turning to
764 the ecological sensibilities encoded in Indigenous knowledges in a way that has sometimes
765 veered toward a (mis)appropriation or overburdening of such non-Western knowledge
766 systems.¹⁰⁷ There has been a solutionist tendency to cut off TEK and other forms of
767 environmental knowledge from their matrices of practice and lived ecologies, effectively
768 reducing them to decontextualized means of “problem solving”. This not only reproduces the
769 problematic assumption of modern technoscience that all proper knowledge is instrumental, it
770 also clouds the view of how different environmental knowledges are *formed* and *enacted*, and
771 what their historical efficacy is — what kinds of action and insight they enable, how they
772 support certain ways of being in the world and not others. Part of the same problem is an
773 undifferentiated celebration of Indigenous knowledge as the new model system for “ecological

¹⁰⁶ Moran, *People and Nature.*, 122.

¹⁰⁷ See Nadasdy, “The Politics of TEK.”

774 stewardship” and the tendency to attest all “pre-modern” societies rich and intimate ecological
775 knowledge. In line with the well-worn trope of the “ecological Indian,”¹⁰⁸ Indigenous peoples,
776 it is often presumed, simply know almost everything about their environment, even if they do
777 not explicate this deep ecological knowledge or articulate it only in “cryptic” or other-than-
778 scientific terms. Hasty ascriptions of comprehensive Indigenous knowledge tend to distract
779 from the specific sources, logics, and methods that different people(s) have relied on to learn
780 and make sense of their environments. What is needed instead are historically and
781 ethnographically specific accounts of how such knowledges are learned, maintained, and
782 transformed within their own sociopolitical and multispecies ecologies, and which nonhuman
783 others are drawn into such ecologies for what reasons.

784 As a final point, we wish to note that even though this article has primarily sought to
785 advance historical and archaeological perspectives, it is attentive to the multispecies
786 negotiations that have become increasingly urgent in our present moment of accelerating
787 extinctions and ecological destruction, as communities of various backgrounds and
788 positionalities find their lives and livelihoods intersect with those of nonhuman others. For
789 example, “rewilding” — one of the many contemporary attempts to restore some of the basic
790 functioning of degraded ecosystems — has been conceptualized through the lens of “human-
791 wildlife conflict,” as so-called “dangerous” animals are reintroduced into landscapes that have
792 been human-dominated for centuries or more.¹⁰⁹ Rather than reducing these animals to their
793 potential for conflict and focusing on (preventing) negative interactions, however, we should
794 realize that such endeavors also offer underestimated opportunities for interspecies learning
795 and that whether we frame them in terms of conflict or conviviality is likely to influence the
796 space of possibilities for living with each other we are able to imagine and the forms of

¹⁰⁸ Nadasdy, “Transcending the Debate over the Ecologically Noble Indian.”

¹⁰⁹ Glentworth et al., “The Place for People in Rewilding.”

797 multispecies solidarity we are willing to pursue.¹¹⁰ *Learning to live with other animals*, then,
798 poses a principal challenge wrought not only by a planet characterized by fundamental
799 ecosystem novelty¹¹¹ but also by new imaginings of how we want to share the planet with other
800 life, a concern reflected in recent debates around “convivial conservation” and the hope to
801 create “long-lasting, engaging and open-ended relationships with nonhumans and
802 ecologies”.¹¹² Yet learning to live with other animals requires a break with entrenched notions
803 of human sovereignty in which even nonessential human interests often trump the most basic
804 existential needs of other creatures. It requires us to move beyond anthropocentric notions of
805 coexistence¹¹³ and to grant nonhuman creatures behavioral plasticity – the capacity, that is, to
806 learn to live with other animals.¹¹⁴

807

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815

¹¹⁰ van Dooren, “Military Snails: Multispecies Solidarities in Hawai’i.”

¹¹¹ Kerr et al., “Widespread Ecological Novelty across the Terrestrial Biosphere.”

¹¹² Büscher and Fletcher, “Towards Convivial Conservation.”

¹¹³ Pooley et al., “Rethinking the Study of Human–Wildlife Coexistence.”

¹¹⁴ For contemporary examples using alternative templates of human-wildlife coexistence, see Panggur et al., “Living in Harmony with Dragons.”; Nair et al., “Sharing Spaces and Entanglements With Big Cats.”

816 **Bibliography**

- 817 Aaris-Sørensen, Kim. *Diversity and Dynamics of the Mammalian Fauna in Denmark*
 818 *throughout the Last Glacial-Interglacial Cycle, 115-0 Kyr BP*. John Wiley & Sons,
 819 2010.
- 820 Allen, Jedediah W. P., and Kristin Andrews. “How Not to Find Over-Imitation in Animals.”
 821 *Human Development*, February 20, 2024, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000537938>.
- 822 Anderson, Kat. *Tending the Wild: Native American Knowledge and the Management of*
 823 *California’s Natural Resources*. University of California Press, 2005.
- 824 Anderson, Virginia DeJohn. *Creatures of Empire: How Domestic Animals Transformed Early*
 825 *America*. Oxford University Press, 2004.
- 826 Andrews, Kristin, Christopher Kelty, and Kulbhushansingh Suryawanshi. “Multi-Species
 827 Societies.” *Behavioral and Brain Sciences* 48 (January 2025): e52.
 828 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X24001109>.
- 829 Baratay, Éric. “Building an Animal History.” In *French Thinking About Animals*, edited by
 830 Louisa Mackenzie and Stephanie Posthumus. Michigan State University Press, 2015.
- 831 Barsh, Russel Lawrence, and Chantelle Marlor. “Driving Bison and Blackfoot Science.”
 832 *Human Ecology* 31, no. 4 (2003): 571–93.
 833 <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:HUEC.0000005514.93842.91>.
- 834 Berger, Peter L., and Thomas A. Luckmann. *The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in*
 835 *the Sociology of Knowledge*. Penguin, 1991.
- 836 Bethke, Brandi. “Revisiting the Horse in Blackfoot Culture: Understanding the Development
 837 of Nomadic Pastoralism on the North American Plains.” *International Journal of*
 838 *Historical Archaeology* 24, no. 1 (2020): 44–61.
- 839 Betts, Matthew w, Mari Hardenberg, and Ian Stirling. “How Animals Create Human History:
 840 Relational Ecology and the Dorset–Polar Bear Connection.” *American Antiquity* 80, no.
 841 1 (2015): 89–112. <https://doi.org/10.7183/0002-7316.79.4.89>.
- 842 Bird-David, Nurit. *Us, Relatives: Scaling and Plural Life in a Forager World*. University of
 843 California Press, 2017.
- 844 Bruyn, P. J. N. de, Cheryl A. Tosh, and Aleks Terauds. “Killer Whale Ecotypes: Is There a
 845 Global Model?” *Biological Reviews* 88, no. 1 (2013): 62–80.
 846 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2012.00239.x>.
- 847 Büscher, Bram, and Robert Fletcher. “Towards Convivial Conservation.” *Conservation &*
 848 *Society* 17, no. 3 (2019): 283–96.
- 849 Cabral, Diogo de Carvalho, and Heta Lähdesmäki. “Multispecies Cultures and Environmental
 850 Change: The Animal (Agency) Turn.” In *The Routledge Handbook of Environmental*
 851 *History*. Routledge, 2023.
- 852 Calarco, Matthew. *Zoographies: The Question of the Animal from Heidegger to Derrida*.
 853 Columbia University Press, 2008.
- 854 Cantor, Mauricio, Damien R. Farine, and Fábio G. Daura-Jorge. “Foraging Synchrony Drives
 855 Resilience in Human–Dolphin Mutualism.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of*
 856 *Sciences* 120, no. 6 (2023): e2207739120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2207739120>.
- 857 Castro, Eduardo Viveiros de. “Cosmological Deixis and Amerindian Perspectivism.” *The*
 858 *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute* 4, no. 3 (1998): 469–88.
- 859 Cat, Jordi. “Essay Review: Scientific Pluralism.” *Philosophy of Science* 79, no. 2 (2012): 317–
 860 25. <https://doi.org/10.1086/664747>.
- 861 Charbonneau, Mathieu, Arianna Curioni, Luke McEllin, and James W. A. Strachan. “Flexible
 862 Cultural Learning Through Action Coordination.” *Perspectives on Psychological*
 863 *Science* 19, no. 1 (2024): 201–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17456916231182923>.

- 864 Chemero, Anthony. “An Outline of a Theory of Affordances.” *Ecological Psychology* 15, no.
865 2 (2003): 181–95.
- 866 Clark, Douglas, Kyle Artelle, Chris Darimont, et al. “Grizzly and Polar Bears as
867 Nonconsumptive Cultural Keystone Species.” *FACETS* 6 (January 2021): 379–93.
868 <https://doi.org/10.1139/facets-2020-0089>.
- 869 Coldicutt, Susan. “Environmental Knowing and Action.” *Environmentalist* 18, no. 4 (1999):
870 251–61. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006545522339>.
- 871 Coles, Bryony. *Beavers in Britain’s Past*. With WARP (Project). WARP Occasional Paper 19.
872 Oxbow Books ; WARP, 2006.
- 873 Cram, Dominic L., Jessica E. M. van der Wal, Natalie Uomini, et al. “The Ecology and
874 Evolution of Human-Wildlife Cooperation.” *People and Nature* 4, no. 4 (2022): 841–
875 55. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10369>.
- 876 Csordas, Thomas J. “Somatic Modes of Attention.” *Cultural Anthropology* 8, no. 2 (1993):
877 135–56.
- 878 Dale, Leigh. “Empire’s Proxy: Sheep and the Colonial Environment.” In *Five Emus to the King*
879 *of Siam*, edited by Helen Tiffin. Rodopi, 2007.
- 880 Damkjar, Eric. “Late Dorset Longhouses: A Look Inside.” In *Contributions to the Study of the*
881 *Dorset Palaeo-Eskimos*. Canadian Museum of Civilization, 2005.
- 882 Descola, Philippe. “Cognition, Perception and Worlding.” *Interdisciplinary Science Reviews*
883 35, nos. 3–4 (2010): 334–40.
- 884 Dooren, Thom van. “Military Snails: Multispecies Solidarities in Hawai‘i.” In *Unsettling*
885 *Extinction*, edited by Roman Bartosch, Ursula K. Heise, and Kate Rigby. Bloomsbury,
886 2026.
- 887 Dutant, Julien. “The Legend of the Justified True Belief Analysis.” *Philosophical Perspectives*
888 29 (2015): 95–145.
- 889 Eerkens, Jelmer W., and Carl P. Lipo. “Cultural Transmission Theory and the Archaeological
890 Record: Providing Context to Understanding Variation and Temporal Changes in
891 Material Culture.” *Journal of Archaeological Research* 15, no. 3 (2007): 239–74.
892 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10814-007-9013-z>.
- 893 Ellis, Erle C., Peter J. Richerson, Alex Mesoudi, Jens-Christian Svenning, John Odling-Smee,
894 and William R. Burnside. “Evolving the Human Niche.” *Proceedings of the National*
895 *Academy of Sciences* 113, no. 31 (2016): E4436–E4436.
896 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1609425113>.
- 897 Ewers, John C. *The Horse in Blackfoot Indian Culture: With Comparative Material from Other*
898 *Western Tribes*. Government Printing Office, 1955.
- 899 Finzsch, Norbert. “‘The Intrusion Therefore of Cattle Is by Itself Sufficient to Produce the
900 Extirpation of the Native Race’: Social Ecological Systems and Ecocide in Conflicts
901 Between Hunter–Gatherers and Commercial Stock Farmers in Australia.” *Settler*
902 *Colonial Studies* 7, no. 2 (2015): 164–91.
- 903 Fleischer, Robert C. “Ladies and Gentes: Maternally Inherited DNA and Ancient Honeyguide
904 Host Races.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 108, no. 44 (2011):
905 17859–60. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1115041108>.
- 906 Flores, Dan L. *Coyote America: A Natural and Supernatural History*. Basic Books, 2016.
- 907 Fogg, Brandy R., Nimachia Howe, and Raymond Pierotti. “Relationships between Indigenous
908 American Peoples and Wolves 1: Wolves as Teachers and Guides.” *Journal of*
909 *Ethnobiology* 35, no. 2 (2015): 262–85. <https://doi.org/10.2993/etbi-35-02-262-285.1>.
- 910 Frank, Adam, Marcelo Gleiser, and Evan Thompson. *The Blind Spot: Why Science Cannot*
911 *Ignore Human Experience*. The MIT Press, 2024.

- 912 Fuentes, Agustín. “NATURALCULTURAL ENCOUNTERS IN BALI: Monkeys, Temples,
913 Tourists, and Ethnoprimatology.” *Cultural Anthropology* 25, no. 4 (2010): 600–624.
914 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1548-1360.2010.01071.x>.
- 915 Gehlen, Arnold. *Man: His Nature and Place in the World*. Columbia University Press, 1988.
- 916 Gelder, Ken, and Rachael Weaver. *Colonial Kangaroo Hunt*. Melbourne University Publishing,
917 2020.
- 918 Gibson, James J. *The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception*. Houghton Mifflin, 1979.
- 919 Glentworth, Joseph, Anna Gilchrist, and Rowan Avery. “The Place for People in Rewilding.”
920 *Conservation Biology* 38, no. 6 (2024): e14318. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.14318>.
- 921 Glock, Hans-Johann. “Animals, Thoughts and Concepts.” *Synthese* 123, no. 1 (2000): 35–64.
- 922 Glock, Hans-Johann. “Non-Human Knowledge and Non-Human Agency.” In *Conceptions of*
923 *Knowledge*, edited by Stefan Tolksdorf. De Gruyter, 2011.
- 924 Grubb, Teryl G., Roy G. Lopez, and Martha M. Ellis. “Winter Scavenging of Ungulate Carrion
925 By Bald Eagles, Common Ravens, and Coyotes In Northern Arizona.” *Journal of*
926 *Raptor Research* 52, no. 4 (2018): 471–83. <https://doi.org/10.3356/JRR-17-93.1>.
- 927 Haidle, M. N., M. Bolus, M. Collard, et al. *The Nature of Culture : An Eight-Grade Model for*
928 *the Evolution and Expansion of Cultural Capacities in Hominins and Other Animals*.
929 July 1, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.4436/jass.93011>.
- 930 Hämäläinen, Pekka. “The Rise and Fall of Plains Indian Horse Cultures.” *The Journal of*
931 *American History* 90, no. 3 (2003): 833–62.
- 932 Hamilakis, Yannis, and Nick J. Overton. “A Multi-Species Archaeology.” *Archaeological*
933 *Dialogues* 20, no. 2 (2013): 159–73. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1380203813000214>.
- 934 Haraway, Donna J. *When Species Meet*. University of Minnesota Press, 2008.
- 935 Hardenberg, Mari. *Trends and Ontology of Artistic Practices of the Dorset Culture 800 BC-*
936 *1300 AD*. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, University of Copenhagen, 2013.
- 937 Heide-Jørgensen, Mp, P. Richard, M. Ramsay, and S. Akeagok. “Three Recent Ice
938 Entrapments of Arctic Cetaceans in West Greenland and the Eastern Canadian High
939 Arctic.” *NAMMCO Scientific Publications* 4 (July 2002): 143.
940 <https://doi.org/10.7557/3.2841>.
- 941 Heyes, Cecilia M. *Cognitive Gadgets: The Cultural Evolution of Thinking*. Harvard University
942 press, 2018.
- 943 Hill, Erica. “Archaeology and Animal Persons: Toward a Prehistory of Human-Animal
944 Relations.” *Environment and Society. Environment and Society* 4, no. 1 (2013): 117–
945 36. <https://doi.org/10.3167/ares.2013.040108>.
- 946 Hjørungdal, Tove. “Reaching Them a Human Paw: Relational Approaches to Maglemose
947 Companions.” *Archaeological Review from Cambridge* 34 (2019): 65–79.
948 <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.59739>.
- 949 Huffman, Michael A. “Animal Self-Medication and Ethno-Medicine: Exploration and
950 Exploitation of the Medicinal Properties of Plants.” *The Proceedings of the Nutrition*
951 *Society* 62, no. 2 (2003): 371–81.
- 952 Huffman, Michael A. “Folklore, Animal Self-Medication, and Phytotherapy—Something Old,
953 Something New, Something Borrowed, Some Things True.” *Planta Med* 88 (2022):
954 187–99.
- 955 Hussain, S. T., S. F. Hellerøe, H. N. Dalager, E. S. Nielsen, M. Vinter, and F. Riede. “Was the
956 Late Glacial Human Occupation of Northernmost Europe Facilitated by Whales? New
957 Data and Perspectives on Lithic Technology and the Paleoecology of the Vendsyssel
958 Area, Northern Jutland, Denmark.” *The Journal of Island and Coastal Archaeology* 0,
959 no. 0 (2024): 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15564894.2023.2277727>.
- 960 Hussain, Shumon T. “Deep Animal Prehistory: Gathering Feral Voices from Vanished
961 Pleistocene Worlds.” In *Beyond Subsistence: Human-Nature Interactions*, edited by

- 962 Keiko Kitagawa, Valentina Tumolo, and Marta Díaz-Zorita Bonilla. CRC 1070
 963 Monographs, 2024.
- 964 Hussain, Shumon T. “The Heath and the Sea: A Speculative Palaeohistory of Multispecies Life
 965 in Northern Jutland, ca 13,300–12,800 Years Ago.” In *A Place for the Heathlands(?)*
 966 *Human-Heath Relations in Deep-Time and Contemporary Perspectives*, edited by
 967 Mette Løvschal and Mark Haughton. Aarhus University Press, 2025.
 968 <https://heathland.place/the-heath-and-the-sea>.
- 969 Hussain, Shumon T., and Nathalie Ø. Brusgaard. “Human-Beaver Cohabitation in the Early
 970 and Mid-Holocene of Northern Europe: Re-Visiting Mesolithic Material Culture and
 971 Ecology Through a Multispecies Lens.” *The Holocene* 34, no. 1 (2024): 25–55.
 972 <https://doi.org/10.1177/09596836231200444>.
- 973 Hyde, Lewis. *Trickster Makes This World: Mischievous, Myth, and Art*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux,
 974 1998.
- 975 Ingold, Tim. *The Perception of the Environment: Essays on Livelihood, Dwelling and Skill*.
 976 Routledge, 2000.
- 977 Jackson, Christine E. “Fishing with Cormorants.” *Archives of Natural History* 24, no. 2 (1997):
 978 189–211. <https://doi.org/10.3366/anh.1997.24.2.189>.
- 979 Jaeger, Johannes, Anna Riedl, Alex Djedovic, John Vervaeke, and Denis Walsh. “Naturalizing
 980 Relevance Realization: Why Agency and Cognition Are Fundamentally Not
 981 Computational.” *Frontiers in Psychology* 15 (June 2024).
 982 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1362658>.
- 983 Jenkins, Harold S. “Gibson’s ‘Affordances’: Evolution of a Pivotal Concept.” *Journal of*
 984 *Scientific Psychology*, December 2008, 34–45.
- 985 Jesmer, Brett R., Jerod A. Merkle, Jacob R. Goheen, et al. “Is Ungulate Migration Culturally
 986 Transmitted? Evidence of Social Learning from Translocated Animals.” *Science* 361,
 987 no. 6406 (2018): 1023–25. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat0985>.
- 988 Kashina, Ekaterina, and Anastasia A. Khramtsova. “In the Company of Bears: The Role and
 989 Significance of the Bear from the Perspective of the Holocene Hunter-Gatherer-Fishers
 990 of the East European Plain Forest Zone (10th–3rd Millennium BC).” In *Bear and*
 991 *Human: Facets of a Multi-Layered Relationship from Past to Recent Times, with*
 992 *Emphasis on Northern Europe*. Brepols, 2023.
- 993 Kellert, Stephen H., Helen E. Longino, and C. Kenneth Waters, eds. *Scientific Pluralism*.
 994 Minnesota Studies in the Philosophy of Science, v. 19. University of Minnesota Press,
 995 2006.
- 996 Kerr, Matthew R., Alejandro Ordonez, Felix Riede, et al. “Widespread Ecological Novelty
 997 across the Terrestrial Biosphere.” *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, March 14, 2025, 1–10.
 998 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-025-02662-2>.
- 999 Kimmerer, Robin Wall. *Braiding Sweetgrass: Indigenous Wisdom, Scientific Knowledge and*
 1000 *the Teachings of Plants*. First paperback edition. Milkweed Editions, 2013.
- 1001 Kimmerer, Robin Wall. *The Democracy of Species*. Green Ideas 10. Penguin Books, 2021.
- 1002 Kockelman, Paul. “Biosemiosis, Technocognition, and Sociogenesis: Selection and
 1003 Significance in a Multiverse of Sieving and Serendipity.” *Current Anthropology* 52, no.
 1004 5 (2011): 711–39. <https://doi.org/10.1086/661708>.
- 1005 Kornblith, Hilary. “Epistemology and Cognitive Ethology.” In *Conceptions of Knowledge*,
 1006 edited by Stefan Tolkdorf. De Gruyter, 2011.
- 1007 Kornblith, Hilary. *Knowledge and Its Place in Nature*. Clarendon Press, 2002.
- 1008 Kuznar, Lawrence A. “Ecological Mutualism in Navajo Corrals: Implications for Navajo
 1009 Environmental Perceptions and Human/Plant Coevolution.” *Journal of*
 1010 *Anthropological Research* 57, no. 1 (2001): 17–39.
 1011 <https://doi.org/10.1086/jar.57.1.3630796>.

- 1012 Laidre, Kristin L., Ian Stirling, James A. Estes, Anatoly Kochnev, and Jason Roberts.
 1013 “Historical and Potential Future Importance of Large Whales as Food for Polar Bears.”
 1014 *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 16, no. 9 (2018): 515–24.
 1015 <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1963>.
- 1016 LaPier, Rosalyn R. *Invisible Reality: Storytellers, Storytakers, and the Supernatural World of*
 1017 *the Blackfeet*. New Visions in Native American and Indigenous Studies. University of
 1018 Nebraska Press, 2017.
- 1019 Lestel, Dominique. “Hybrid Communities.” *Angelaki* 19, no. 3 (2014): 61–73.
- 1020 Lezama-Núñez, Paulina R., Dídac Santos-Fita, and José R. Vallejo. “Herding Ecologies and
 1021 Ongoing Plant Domestication Processes in the Americas.” *Frontiers in Plant Science* 9
 1022 (May 2018). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.00649>.
- 1023 Liarsou, Alexandra. “Interactions between the Beaver (*Castor Fiber L.*) and Human Societies:
 1024 A Long-Term Archaeological and Historical Approach.” *Archaeological Review from*
 1025 *Cambridge* 28, no. 2 (2013): 171–85.
- 1026 Lorimer, Jamie, and Timothy Hodgetts. *More-than-Human*. Routledge, 2024.
- 1027 Manzi, Maya, and Oliver T. Coomes. “Cormorant Fishing in Southwestern China: A Traditional
 1028 Fishery Under Siege*.” *Geographical Review* 92, no. 4 (2002): 597–603. World.
- 1029 Marchesini, Roberto. *The Creative Animal: How Every Animal Builds Its Own Existence*.
 1030 Springer, 2022.
- 1031 Marchesini, Roberto. “The Theriosphere.” *Angelaki* 21, no. 1 (2016): 113–35.
- 1032 Massimi, Michela. *Perspectival Realism*. Oxford Studies in Philos Science Series. Oxford
 1033 University Press, 2022.
- 1034 Mesoudi, Alex. *Cultural Evolution: How Darwinian Theory Can Explain Human Culture and*
 1035 *Synthesize the Social Sciences*. University of Chicago Press, 2011.
 1036 <https://press.uchicago.edu/ucp/books/book/chicago/C/bo8787504.html>.
- 1037 Migliano, Andrea Bamberg, and Lucio Vinicius. “The Origins of Human Cumulative Culture:
 1038 From the Foraging Niche to Collective Intelligence.” *Philosophical Transactions of the*
 1039 *Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 377, no. 1843 (2021): 20200317.
 1040 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2020.0317>.
- 1041 Milton, Shaun. “The Transvaal Beef Frontier: Environment, Markets and the Ideology of
 1042 Development, 1902-1942.” In *Ecology and Empire: Environmental History of Settler*
 1043 *Societies*, edited by Tom Griffiths and Libby Robin. Edinburgh University Press, 1997.
- 1044 Mitchell, Peter. *Horse Nations: The Worldwide Impact of the Horse on Indigenous Societies*
 1045 *Post-1492*. Oxford University Press, 2015.
- 1046 Moore, John H. *The Cheyenne Nation: A Social and Demographic History*. University of
 1047 Nebraska Press, 1987.
- 1048 Moran, Emilio F. *People and Nature: An Introduction to Human Ecological Relations*. Second
 1049 edition. John Wiley Blackwell, 2017.
- 1050 Morelli, Federico, Anna Maria Kubicka, Piotr Tryjanowski, and Emma Nelson. “The Vulture
 1051 in the Sky and the Hominin on the Land: Three Million Years of Human–Vulture
 1052 Interaction.” *Anthrozoös* 28, no. 3 (2015): 449–68.
 1053 <https://doi.org/10.1080/08927936.2015.1052279>.
- 1054 Mueller, Natalie G., Robert N. Spengler, Ashley Glenn, and Kunsang Lama. “Bison,
 1055 Anthropogenic Fire, and the Origins of Agriculture in Eastern North America.” *The*
 1056 *Anthropocene Review* 8, no. 2 (2021): 141–58.
- 1057 Murray, Maribeth Suzanne. “Prehistoric Use of Ringed Seals: A Zooarchaeological Study from
 1058 Arctic Canada.” *Environmental Archaeology*, ahead of print, April 1, 2005. World.
 1059 <https://doi.org/10.1179/env.2005.10.1.19>.

- 1060 Nadasdy, Paul. “The Gift in the Animal: The Ontology of Hunting and Human-Animal
1061 Sociality.” *American Ethnologist* 34, no. 1 (2007): 25–43.
1062 <https://doi.org/10.1525/ae.2007.34.1.25>.
- 1063 Nadasdy, Paul. “The Politics of Tek: Power and the ‘Integration’ of Knowledge.” *Arctic*
1064 *Anthropology* 36, no. 1/2 (1999): 1–18.
- 1065 Nadasdy, Paul. “Transcending the Debate over the Ecologically Noble Indian: Indigenous
1066 Peoples and Environmentalism.” *Ethnohistory* 52, no. 2 (2005): 291–331.
1067 <https://doi.org/10.1215/00141801-52-2-291>.
- 1068 Nair, Ramya, Dhee, Omkar Patil, et al. “Sharing Spaces and Entanglements With Big Cats: The
1069 Warli and Their Waghoba in Maharashtra, India.” *Frontiers in Conservation Science* 2
1070 (June 2021). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcosc.2021.683356>.
- 1071 Nance, Susan, ed. *The Historical Animal*. Syracuse University Press, 2015.
- 1072 Natoli, Eugenia, Carla Litchfield, and Dominique Pontier. “Coexistence between Humans and
1073 ‘Misunderstood’ Domestic Cats in the Anthropocene: Exploring Behavioural Plasticity
1074 as a Gatekeeper of Evolution.” *Animals* 12, no. 13 (2022): 1717.
1075 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani12131717>.
- 1076 Odling-Smee, F. John, Kevin N. Laland, and Marcus W. Feldman. *Niche Construction: The*
1077 *Neglected Process in Evolution*. Monographs in Population Biology, no. 37. Princeton
1078 University Press, 2003.
- 1079 Ohrem, Dominik. “A Declaration of Interdependence: American History and the Challenges of
1080 Postanthropocentric Historiography.” In *American Beasts: Perspectives on Animals*
1081 *and Animality in U.S. Culture, 1776-1920*, edited by Dominik Ohrem. Neofelis, 2017.
- 1082 Ohrem, Dominik. “An Address from Elsewhere: Vulnerability, Relationality, and Conceptions
1083 of Creaturely Embodiment.” In *Beyond the Human-Animal Divide: Creaturely Lives in*
1084 *Literature and Culture*, edited by Dominik Ohrem and Roman Bartosch. Palgrave
1085 Macmillan, 2017.
- 1086 Ohrem, Dominik. “Human-Animal Relations and the Ontopolitics of Civilization in
1087 Nineteenth-Century U.S. Settler Culture.” PhD dissertation, University of Cologne,
1088 2025.
- 1089 Oma Armstrong, Kristin. *The Sheep People: The Ontology of Making Lives, Building Homes*
1090 *and Forging Herds in Early Bronze Age Norway*. Equinox Publishing Ltd, 2018.
- 1091 Osborn, Alan J. “Ecological Aspects of Equestrian Adaptations in Aboriginal North America.”
1092 *American Anthropologist* 85, no. 3 (1983): 563–91.
- 1093 Panggur, Maria Rosdalima, Ayu Wijayanti, and Ardiantiono. “Living in Harmony with
1094 Dragons.” *Current Conservation* 17, no. 4 (2023): 19–24.
- 1095 Parker, Dan, Kylie Soanes, and Stanislav Roudavski. “Interspecies Cultures and Future
1096 Design.” *Transpositiones* 1, no. 1 (2022): 183–236.
1097 <https://doi.org/10.14220/trns.2022.1.1.183>.
- 1098 Pastoors, Andreas, and Tilman Lenssen-Erz, eds. *Reading Prehistoric Human Tracks: Methods*
1099 *& Material*. Springer Nature, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-60406-6>.
- 1100 Petitt, Andrea, and Keri Brandt-Off. “Zoocialization: Learning Together, Becoming Together
1101 in a Multispecies Triad.” *Society & Animals* 1, no. aop (2022): 1–18.
1102 <https://doi.org/10.1163/15685306-bja10082>.
- 1103 Pierotti, Raymond, and Brandy R. Fogg. *The First Domestication: How Wolves and Humans*
1104 *Coevolved*. Yale University Press, 2017.
- 1105 Plessis, Pierre du. “Tracking Meat of the Sand: Noticing Multispecies Landscapes in the
1106 Kalahari.” *Environmental Humanities* 14, no. 1 (2022): 49–70.
1107 <https://doi.org/10.1215/22011919-9481429>.

- 1108 Plumet, Patrick. “Le Foyer Dans l’Arctique.” In *Nature et Fonction Des Foyers Préhistoriques*.
 1109 Actes du Colloque International de Nemours 1987. Memoirs du Musée de Préhistoire
 1110 d’Ile de France, 1989.
- 1111 Polanyi, Michael. *Personal Knowledge: Towards a Post-Critical Philosophy*. 2nd ed.
 1112 University of Chicago Press, 1962.
- 1113 Pooley, Simon, Saloni Bhatia, and Anirudhkumar Vasava. “Rethinking the Study of Human–
 1114 Wildlife Coexistence.” *Conservation Biology* 35, no. 3 (2021): 784–93.
 1115 <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13653>.
- 1116 Ramsey, Grant. “Culture in Humans and Other Animals.” *Biology & Philosophy* 28, no. 3
 1117 (2013): 457–79. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10539-012-9347-x>.
- 1118 Read, Catherine, and Agnes Szokolszky. “What Animals Can Do: Agency, Mutuality, and
 1119 Adaptation.” *Biological Theory* 19, no. 3 (2024): 198–208.
- 1120 Rockman, Marcy. “Knowledge and Learning in the Archaeology of Colonization.” In *The*
 1121 *Colonization of Unfamiliar Landscapes*. Routledge, 2003.
- 1122 Rockman, Marcy. “Landscape Learning in Relation to Evolutionary Theory.” In
 1123 *Macroevolution in Human Prehistory: Evolutionary Theory and Processual*
 1124 *Archaeology*, edited by Anna Prentiss, Ian Kuijt, and James C. Chatters. Springer, 2009.
 1125 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-0682-3_3.
- 1126 Rodriguez, Eloy, and Richard Wrangham. “Zoopharmacognosy: The Use of Medicinal Plants
 1127 by Animals.” In *Phytochemical Potential of Tropical Plants*, edited by Kelsey R.
 1128 Downum, John T. Romeo, and Helen A. Stafford. Springer, 1993.
- 1129 Roe, Frank Gilbert. *The Indian and the Horse*. University of Oklahoma Press, 1955.
- 1130 Roscher, Mieke, André Krebber, and Brett Mizelle, eds. *Handbook of Historical Animal*
 1131 *Studies*. De Gruyter, 2021.
- 1132 Sasaki, Takao, and Dora Biro. “Cumulative Culture Can Emerge from Collective Intelligence
 1133 in Animal Groups.” *Nature Communications* 8, no. 1 (2017): 15049.
 1134 <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms15049>.
- 1135 Savage, Candace. *Prairie: A Natural History of the Heart of North America*. 2nd ed. Greystone
 1136 Books, 2020.
- 1137 Schmölcke, Ulrich, Daniel Groß, and Elena A. Nikulina. “Bears and Beavers: ‘The Browns’ in
 1138 Daily Life and Spiritual World.” In *Interaction without Borders. Exemplary*
 1139 *Archaeological Research at the Beginning of the 21st Century*. Stiftung Schleswig-
 1140 Holsteinische Landesmuseen, 2017.
- 1141 Serpell, James A. “Commensalism or Cross-Species Adoption? A Critical Review of Theories
 1142 of Wolf Domestication.” *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 8 (April 2021): 662370.
 1143 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2021.662370>.
- 1144 Shennan, Stephen. *Genes, Memes and Human History: Darwinian Archaeology and Cultural*
 1145 *Evolution*. 1. publ. Thames & Hudson, 2002.
- 1146 Sherow, James E. *The Grasslands of the United States: An Environmental History*. ABC-CLIO,
 1147 2007.
- 1148 Sherow, James E. “Workings of the Geodialectic: High Plains Indians and Their Horses in the
 1149 Region of the Arkansas River Valley, 1800-1870.” *Environmental History Review* 16,
 1150 no. 2 (1992): 61–84.
- 1151 Shipman, Pat. *The Invaders: How Humans and Their Dogs Drove Neanderthals to Extinction*.
 1152 First Harvard University Press paperback edition. Harvard University Press, 2017.
- 1153 Slagsvold, Tore, and Karen L. Wiebe. “Social Learning in Birds and Its Role in Shaping a
 1154 Foraging Niche.” *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological*
 1155 *Sciences* 366, no. 1567 (2011): 969–77. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2010.0343>.
- 1156 Sorabji, Richard. *Animal Minds and Human Morals: The Origins of the Western Debate*.
 1157 Cornell University Press, 1993.

- 1158 Sosa, Ernest. “Human Knowledge, Animal and Reflective: Reply to Robert Audi, John Greco,
1159 and Hilary Kornblith.” In *Ernest Sosa and His Critics*, edited by John Greco. Blackwell,
1160 2004.
- 1161 Sosa, Ernest. “Knowledge and Intellectual Virtue.” *The Monist* 68, no. 2 (1985): 226–45.
- 1162 Soucy, Shannon M., Jinling Huang, and Johann Peter Gogarten. “Horizontal Gene Transfer:
1163 Building the Web of Life.” *Nature Reviews Genetics* 16, no. 8 (2015): 472–82.
1164 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg3962>.
- 1165 Specht, Joshua. “Animal History after Its Triumph: Unexpected Animals, Evolutionary
1166 Approaches, and the Animal Lens.” *History Compass* 14, no. 7 (2016): 326–36.
- 1167 Spengler, Robert N., and Natalie G. Mueller. “Grazing Animals Drove Domestication of Grain
1168 Crops.” *Nature Plants* 5, no. 7 (2019): 656–62. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41477-019-0470-4>.
- 1170 Speth, John D. “13,000 Years of Communal Bison Hunting in Western North America.” In *The
1171 Oxford Handbook of Zooarchaeology*. Oxford University Press, 2017.
- 1172 Spottiswoode, Claire N., Keith S. Begg, and Colleen M. Begg. “Reciprocal Signaling in
1173 Honeyguide-Human Mutualism.” *Science* 353, no. 6297 (2016): 387–89.
1174 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaf4885>.
- 1175 Sueur, Cédric, and Michael A. Huffman. “Co-Cultures: Exploring Interspecies Culture among
1176 Humans and Other Animals.” *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 0, no. 0 (2024).
1177 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2024.05.011>.
- 1178 Swanson, Heather Anne, Marianne E. Lien, and Gro Ween, eds. *Domestication Gone Wild:
1179 Politics and Practices of Multispecies Relations*. Duke University Press, 2018.
- 1180 Sykes, Naomi Jane. *Beastly Questions: Animal Answers to Archaeological Issues*. Bloomsbury
1181 Academic, 2015.
- 1182 Tallis, Raymond. *The Knowing Animal: A Philosophical Inquiry Into Knowledge and Truth*.
1183 Edinburgh University Press, 2005.
- 1184 Telfer, Wendy R., and Murray J. Garde. “Indigenous Knowledge of Rock Kangaroo Ecology
1185 in Western Arnhem Land, Australia.” *Human Ecology* 34, no. 3 (2006): 379–406.
- 1186 Turri, John. “Is Knowledge Justified True Belief?” *Synthese* 184, no. 3 (2012): 247–59.
- 1187 Tyler, Tom. *Ciferae: A Bestiary in Five Fingers*. University of Minnesota Press, 2012.
- 1188 Wall Kimmerer, Robin. *The Serviceberry*. Scribner, 2024.
- 1189 Walsh, D. M. *Organisms, Agency, and Evolution*. Cambridge University Press, 2015.
- 1190 West, Elliott. *The Contested Plains: Indians, Goldseekers, and the Rush to Colorado*.
1191 University Press of Kansas, 1998.
- 1192 West, Elliott. *The Way to the West: Essays on the Central Plains*. University of New Mexico
1193 Press, 1995.
- 1194 West-Eberhard, Mary Jane. *Developmental Plasticity and Evolution*. Oxford University Press,
1195 2003.
- 1196 Whitehead, Hal, and Luke Rendell. *The Cultural Lives of Whales and Dolphins*. University of
1197 Chicago Press, 2015.
- 1198 Whitehead, Hal, Tim D. Smith, and Luke Rendell. “Adaptation of Sperm Whales to Open-Boat
1199 Whalers: Rapid Social Learning on a Large Scale?” *Biology Letters* 17, no. 3 (2021):
1200 20210030.
- 1201 Whiten, Andrew. “The Burgeoning Reach of Animal Culture.” *Science* 372, no. 6537 (2021):
1202 eabe6514. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abe6514>.
- 1203 Wood, Brian M., Herman Pontzer, David A. Raichlen, and Frank W. Marlowe. “Mutualism and
1204 Manipulation in Hadza–Honeyguide Interactions.” *Evolution and Human Behavior* 35,
1205 no. 6 (2014): 540–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evolhumbehav.2014.07.007>.
- 1206 Wood, Lara A., Rachel L. Kendal, and Emma G. Flynn. “Context-Dependent Model-Based
1207 Biases in Cultural Transmission: Children’s Imitation Is Affected by Model Age Over

1208 Model Knowledge State.” *Evolution and Human Behavior* 33, no. 4 (2012): 387–94.
1209 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evolhumbehav.2011.11.010>.
1210 Zhilin, Mikhail. “Beaver Mandible Tools in the Mesolithic of the Forest Zone of Eastern
1211 Europe and Urals.” *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 30 (April 2020):
1212 102199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2020.102199>.
1213